

Supplementary Information for Low dinosaur biodiversity in central China two million years prior to the end-Cretaceous mass extinction

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Dataset S1

Supplementary Information Text

Geological Setting, Stratigraphy, and Sampling. The Shanyang Basin (33°31'07"N, 109°58'39"E) is located in Shanyang County, southern Shaanxi Province, which is ~5 km wide (North-South) and ~22 km long (East-West) (Fig. 1). The basin initiated in the Cretaceous as an extensional basin controlled by a dip-slip fault named the Shanyang Fault on its southern margin. The strata of the basin mainly dip to the south, with an angle of 10–20°.

The basement of the Shanyang Basin is composed of the Upper Paleozoic rock units. The Upper Devonian Liuling Formation that consists of schist and slate crops out in the north. The Upper Carboniferous Tiechangpu Formation, consisting of crystalline limestone and slate intercalated with volcanic agglomerate rocks, crops out near the south margin (Fig. 1). The Mesozoic and Cenozoic strata of the Shanyang Basin are divided into three stratigraphic units, from bottom to top, including the Upper Cretaceous Shanyang Formation, the Paleocene Juanling Formation, and the Oligocene Guanyinsi Formation (Fig. 1).

The Shanyang Formation consists of brownish-red and purplish-red thick bedded conglomerates, sandy conglomerates, argillaceous siltstones, and sandstones. The Shanyang Formation can be divided further into two members. Member 1 is dominated by thick-bedded conglomerates, partially interbedded with argillaceous siltstones and calcareous nodules. Member 2 is composed mainly of interbedded gravelly sandstones and sandy conglomerates. Abundant Late Cretaceous dinosaur eggshell fossils are found in both members (1), indicating that the Shanyang Formation was deposited in the Late Cretaceous. The Juanling Formation consists of intercalated yellowish-red argillaceous siltstones and gravelly-sandy mudstones, and it is distributed mainly in the Juanlinggou area, the eastern part of the basin. Paleocene mammalian fossils, such as *Bemalambda*, have been discovered in the Juanling Formation (1). The overlying Guanyinsi Formation is confined to a limited area on the southern margin of the basin.

We collected 3538 paleomagnetic samples from 1180 stratigraphic levels across four representative measured sections, namely Sigou, Dongbeigou, Juanlingcao, and Niupanggou sections in the Shanyang Basin (Fig. 1). The samples were drilled using a portable gasoline-powered drilling machine. The cores were orientated *in situ* with magnetic and solar compasses. Paleomagnetic samples (2.54 cm in diameter) were cut into standard cylinder specimens 2.20 cm in length in the laboratory, and the remaining fragmented samples were used for rock magnetic measurements.

We applied the strata attitude and the GPS information acquired by using the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) to calculate the true stratigraphic thickness among different sites (Fig. S2, Tables S1–S3) in the Dongbeigou, Juanlingcao, and Niupanggou sections if there is thick conglomerate interlayer. The sampling interval was ~0.3 m in the Sigou section, and we measured the true thickness of the Sigou section directly with a wooden meter stick.

Rock magnetism. Hysteresis loops, acquisition curves of the isothermal remanent magnetizations (IRMs), and back-field demagnetization curves were measured using Vibrating Sample Magnetometers (VSM 3900 and VSM 8600). Stepwise thermal demagnetization of the three orthogonal component IRMs were used to characterize the magnetic remanence carriers of 48 selected specimens. The magnetic minerals can be distinguished by their unblocking temperatures (2). Selected specimens yielded composite IRMs by being magnetized in successively smaller fields along three orthogonal axes, namely, 2.50 T along the Z-axis, 0.50 T along the Y-axis, and 0.05 T along the X-axis. Pulse magnetizers (2G660 and ASC IM-10-30) were used to apply the magnetic field. These specimens were then subjected to progressive thermal demagnetization up to 690°C at 10–50°C intervals.

A total of 38 representative samples from four sections were measured using Vibrating Sample Magnetometers (VSM 3900 and VSM 8600) to acquire their hysteresis loops. The hysteresis loops corrected for high-field slope contribution show that the coercivities of the specimens are ~20–40 mT (Fig. S3), and some loops present a wasp-waisted behavior (Fig. S3B-C), indicative of at least two coercivity components in the samples.

The medium- and high-coercivity components exhibit an unblocking temperature of ~660°C (Fig. S3D), indicating the presence of maghemite or hematite in specimen SYDBG8-7. The low-coercivity component decreases to nearly zero at about 580°C (Fig. S3D), indicative of the

existence of magnetite. The thermal demagnetization curve of the three orthogonal component IRMs of sample SYDBG9-8 (Fig. S3E) shows a similar characteristic to sample SYDBG8-7. Sample SYNPG1-24 shows lower unblocking temperatures with ~550°C and ~620°C for low- and high-coercivity components, respectively (Fig. S3F), implying that the dominant magnetic remanence carriers are possibly low-titanium magnetite and partially oxidized magnetite.

The rock magnetic results suggest that the dominant magnetic minerals (e.g., magnetite, hematite) in the sediments of the Shanyang Basin can retain a faithful record of paleomagnetic information.

Magnetostratigraphy

Experimental procedures. Magnetic remanence measurements of the natural remanent magnetization (NRM) and the remanences after thermal demagnetization were performed by a three-axis cryogenic magnetometer (2G 760) in a magnetically shielded room (residual field < 300 nT). A total of 919 specimens were subjected to progressive thermal demagnetization (22 steps) up to a maximum temperature of 690°C, with intervals of 25–50°C below 610°C and 10°C above 610°C, using the thermal demagnetizers (MMTD80A and ASC TD-48) with a residual magnetic field of less than 20 nT. The characteristic remanent magnetization (ChRM) of each specimen was isolated effectively after removal of the soft secondary components of magnetization. The orthogonal diagrams (3) and the least-squares fitting technique (4) were used to compute the demagnetization results and the principal component directions. The criteria of selecting the demagnetization points (Tables S5–S9) for calculating the ChRM directions are as follows: (1) at least four consecutive demagnetization temperature points; (2) the maximum angular deviation (MAD) is less than 15°; and (3) selecting the higher temperature points when possible, particularly when the directions of higher temperature components differ from the lower temperature components.

Rock magnetism and paleomagnetism measurements were performed at the Paleomagnetism and Geochronology Laboratory (PGL) of the Institute of Geology and Geophysics, Chinese Academy of Sciences in Beijing, and the Environmental Magnetism Laboratory and Rock Magnetism Laboratory of China University of Geosciences in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China.

Paleomagnetic results. The representative Zijderveld diagrams (3) for the demagnetized specimens from the Shanyang Basin are presented in Figs. S4–S6. The demagnetization results show that a secondary magnetic component, probably of viscous remanent magnetization (VRM), was primarily removed at temperatures lower than 300°C. The high-stability ChRM component was separated between 300°C and 690°C (Figs. S4–S6). These behaviors indicate that magnetite, hematite, or maghemite dominate the ChRM carriers in the specimens. After thermal demagnetization, a total of 558 specimens (61%) yielded reliable ChRM directions (Tables S5–S8).

The boundary conglomerate characterized by a ~10–30 m conglomerate bed and overlying reduction spots can be identified as correlating to different sampled sections in the Shanyang Basin. Based on the distribution of fossils in the sections (Fig. 2), the Cretaceous-Paleogene boundary (KPB) is close to or within the boundary conglomerate layer (1).

The bottom sandstone interbeds within the conglomerate strata of Member 1 of the Shanyang Formation in the Dongbeigou section recorded a normal polarity, in accordance with the Juanlingcao section (Fig. 2, Fig. S7). The sandstone specimens that were collected just above the underlying conglomerate strata also record a normal polarity (Fig. 2I, ~360 m), which probably belongs to polarity N5 of the Dongbeigou section based on our consideration of the rapid accumulation of the underlying conglomerate strata as in the Juanlingcao section (Fig. 2A–C). Therefore, the polarities N3–R4 of the Dongbeigou section can be correlated readily with Chrons C30n–C31r, respectively (Fig. 2I).

Five magnetozones (three normal polarities, two reverse polarities) are recognized in the Sigou section (Fig. 2D–F, Fig. S7). The boundary conglomerate is at the stratigraphic level of ~200–220 m (Fig. 2D), and the specimens near this marker layer record a reversed polarity (R2), which indicates polarity R2 (193.2–250.0 m) corresponding to Chron C29r (Fig. 2F and 2J). Thus, polarity N2 (250.0–316.0 m) should be correlated with Chron C29n, and polarities N3–N4 can be correlated

with Chrons C30n–C31n (Fig. 2F and 2J). Based on the layer of boundary conglomerate, we can also correlate five polarities of the Niupanggou section with the GPTS (Fig. S7).

The magnetostratigraphy of these representative sections (Juanlingcao section, Dongbeigou section, Sigou section, and Niupanggou section) provides a solid geochronological framework for the Shanyang Basin.

Conglomerate test and reversals test

The sediments of the Shanyang Basin are principally red beds. As largely pervasive remagnetizations have been reported in red beds (5-8), conglomerate and reversals tests were applied to assess the originality and reliability of ChRMs in the Shanyang Basin.

We conducted a conglomerate test on the sandy conglomerate rocks of the Dongbeigou section to determine whether the samples were remagnetized after their formation. We collected 18 samples from nine sandstone conglomerates from the same layer. A total of 10 representative samples were selected for the conglomerate test. After thermal demagnetization, reliable ChRM directions were isolated from seven specimens (Fig. S9).

Zijderveld plots show that most of the conglomerate specimens recorded reliable ChRM directions by magnetite (Fig. S9C, E, G), hematite (Fig. S9D), and maghemite (Fig. S9H). Equal area projections of the conglomerate specimens (Fig. S9F) show that different conglomerates carried different ChRM directions (e.g., SYDBG4g-5-1 and SYDBG4g-6-1). By contrast, different specimens from the same conglomerate possess consistent directions (e.g., SYDBG4g-7-1 and SYDBG4g-7-2A), indicating uniform magnetization existed in the same conglomerate, while the ChRM directions of different conglomerates pointed to random directions.

We applied the Watson test (9) to test the conglomerate directional data set for randomness. The length of the resultant vector (R value) of the ChRM directions of the conglomerate specimens is 0.66 using the Fisher statistic. The parameter R_0 was defined for testing the randomness of a given data set (9). If $R > R_0$, then the hypothesis is not accepted at the 95% or 99% confidence levels. If $R < R_0$, then the hypothesis is accepted at the 95% or 99% confidence level. R_0 for seven specimens (4.18 at the 95% and 4.89 at the 99% confidence levels, respectively) was given by Watson (9). As R (0.66) $< R_0$ (4.18 or 4.89), the hypothesis that conglomerate directions are random is accepted at the 95% and 99% confidence levels, implying that the remanent magnetizations of the conglomerates were acquired before the formation of the conglomerate layer.

The reversals test can be applied to the two polarities in a given data collection to see if they are antipodal with mean directions 180° apart, and it has been performed for the ChRM data from four sections in the Shanyang Basin. The basis of this test is that if the magnetizations are remagnetized by another component, then both the normal and the reverse directions should be shifted towards the direction of the remagnetization component, and they would no longer be 180° apart (10). The normal and reverse polarity directions from the Dongbeigou, Sigou, and Niupanggou sections were subjected to the Fisherian form of the reversals test (11) and the bootstrap reversals test (12) (Figs. S10–S12).

However, we noted that V_∞ value (26.4) is larger than the V_{crit} value (5.9) in the Juanlingcao section (Fig. S11D), indicating that the Fisher mean directions of the normal and reversed polarities are not antipodal. In addition, the confidence bounds from the positive and negative polarity data sets overlap for the Y component but not for the X and Z components in the Juanlingcao section (Fig. S12G–I). The predicted declination and inclination calculated from apparent polar wander paths of Besse *et al.* (13) were about 11.5° and 50.5° from ~ 70 Ma to ~ 65 Ma in the Shanyang Basin, and the Fisher mean inclination from the lower hemisphere of the Juanlingcao section is only 33.8° . The data from the lower hemisphere are mainly from the N2 and N3 polarities (Fig. S7K) and elongate in an east-west direction (Fig. S11C). Hence, we assume that the paleomagnetic directions from the upper layers (e.g., 500–980 m) of the Juanlingcao section were flattened because of compaction (12). The paleomagnetic result of the Juanlingcao section is congruent with the Dongbeigou and Sigou sections (Fig. S7). Therefore, we conclude that the paleomagnetic results of the Juanlingcao section are reliable as the compaction-induced inclination shallowing did not change their polarities.

Hence, the conglomerate test and reversals test provide solid evidence that the remanent magnetization recorded by the sediments of the Shanyang Basin were not remagnetized, and thus can be applied to establish a magnetostratigraphic framework for the Shanyang Basin.

Cyclostratigraphy

A total of 5466 samples were collected from stratigraphic levels from 16 to 316.5 m with a resolution of ~5 cm. Powder samples were measured with Bartington MS2 Magnetic Susceptibility System.

The magnetic susceptibility (MS) series was divided into four parts (16–80 m, 80–160 m, 165–242 m, and 245–316.5 m) for spectral analysis based on variations in sediment accumulation rate. The MS data series in these four parts were prewhitened in Kaleidagraph software by subtracting 25% weighted averages to remove long-term trends. Based on the paleomagnetic results and calculated sediment accumulation rates, the dominant spectral components (short and long eccentricity cycles, obliquity, and precession cycles) were extracted using Gauss band-pass filtering in AnalySeries 2.0.8 software (14). The power spectra of the untuned and tuned data were analyzed by the 2π -MultiTaper Method (MTM) using the SSA-MTM Toolkit with robust red noise models at the mean, 90%, 95%, and 99% confidence levels (15).

Based on the mean sediment accumulation rate constrained by paleomagnetic patterns and the comparison between frequency ratio of proxy and ratios of Milankovitch frequencies, the dominant ~10.0–8.0 m, and ~3.2 m cycles in the 16.0 to 80.0 m intervals represent ~100-kyr eccentricity and 41-kyr obliquity cycles, respectively (Fig. S13E). The 80.0 to 160.0 m intervals show dominant cycles at ~10.0–8.0 m, ~5.6 m, and ~4.0–3.7 m. The ~10.0–8.0 m cycles are interpreted as ~100-kyr eccentricity cycles (Fig. S13D). The 165.0–242.0 m interval is dominated by ~11.0 m cycles, representing ~100-kyr cycles (Fig. S13C). The interval 245.0–316.5 m displays dominant cycles with ~12.0 m and ~3.1 m cycles (Fig. S13B). Here, the ~12.0 m cycles likely represent ~100-kyr eccentricity cycles based on paleomagnetic results. In total, we counted 38 eccentricity cycles of ~100 kyr (Fig. S13). Our tuning indicates an ~3.9-million-year duration for the 16.0 to 316.5 m sampling interval (Fig. S13).

According to the marker layers (e.g., the conglomerate layers, the magnetic polarity transition layers) (Fig. S7), we can establish an integrated lithostratigraphy for the Shanyang Basin (Fig. 2). Hence, the cyclostratigraphic analysis of the Sigou section can be used to determine the ages of the dinosaur fossils in the Niupanggou section (Fig. 2, Fig. S7).

The Late Cretaceous Dinosaur Fossils

The dinosaur eggshells in the Shanyang Basin. More than 1000 dinosaur eggshell fragments and several (in)complete eggs were collected from 44 continuous levels of the Niupanggou and Juanlingcao sections (Fig. S14). The representative sections of the eggshells were examined under normal and orthogonal polarized light, using a polarizing microscope for parataxonomic identification. The identifications and descriptions of the dinosaurian eggshell fossils namely *Macroolithus yaotunensis*, *Elongatoolithus elongatus* and *Stromatoolithus pinglingensis* and the turtle eggshell taxon *Shanyangoolithus shanyangensis* are as follows.

Elongatoolithidae Zhao, 1975

Elongatoolithus Zhao, 1975

Elongatoolithus elongatus Zhao, 1975

Fig. S16

Description. Dispersituberculate to linearituberculate ornamentation, linear density of ridges ranges from 7 to 13 per centimeter. Eggshell thickness ranges between 0.77 and 1.01 mm without ornamentation and 0.89 to 1.34 mm when ornamented. The transition between the cone layer and the column layer is gradual. Thickness of the cone layer ranges from 0.14 to 0.28 mm.

Macroolithus Zhao, 1975

Macroolithus yaotunensis Zhao, 1975

Fig. S17

Description. Dispersituberculate to linearituberculate ornamentation, linear density of ridges ranges from 7 to 9 per centimeter. Eggshell thickness ranges from 1.29 to 1.55 mm without

ornamentation, and 1.49 to 1.92 mm when ornamented. Distinct undulating transition between the cone layer and the column layer. Thickness of the cone layer ranges between 0.34 and 0.44 mm.

Oofamily indet.

Stromatoolithus Zhao et al., 1991

Stromatoolithus pinglingensis Zhao et al., 1991

Fig. S18

Description. Sagenotuberculate ornamentation consists of nodes that are often elongated, connected, or fused into reticulated ridges, while some are regularly round and scattered. Node density and diameter average 119 per square centimeter and 0.58 mm, respectively. The thickness of the eggshell ranges between 1.11 and 1.49 mm without ornamentation, and 1.22 to 1.63 mm with ornamentation. The eggshell is composed of one layer of shell units that are highly fused together, and the boundary between adjacent shell units is not clear. The spherulitic shell unit is composed of calcite crystals that radiate in wedges from the organic core, and they do not have a branch. The mammillae are nearly round in tangential view, and have a density of about 587.4 per square centimeter, with a diameter ranging between 96.0 and 240.8 μm . The pore systems are composed of tubular canals with slightly changing diameters and smooth edges, and the canals are usually circular or elliptical in tangential view. The density of pores ranges between 257.0 and 385.8 per square centimeter and their diameter range from 44.8 to 160.4 μm . Pore openings are circular, oval, or slightly elongated and silt-like in shape. Accretion lines are developed and evenly distributed throughout the eggshell.

Testudoolithidae Hirsch 1996

Shanyangoolithus Zhang et Xue, 1996

Shanyangoolithus shanyangensis Zhang et Xue, 1996

Fig. S19

Description. No ornamentation. This thin eggshell ranges in thickness between 0.50 and 0.59 mm. The eggshell is composed of one layer of loosely arranged fan shaped radiating needle-like crystals (see the Plate IX, 1c in Xue *et al.* (1)). Intervals between the eggshell units are developed.

The global Late Cretaceous dinosaurs. Condamine *et al.* (16) have assembled a dataset of Late Cretaceous dinosaur fossils comprising 1636 global occurrences retrieved using the Paleobiology Database through the FossilWorks website (fossilworks.org/). We plotted the locations (Table S11) of the dinosaur occurrences on a plate tectonic map of the Earth ~66.0 Ma (Fig. 6).

Fig. S1. Outcrops and paleomagnetic sampling in the Shanyang Basin. An angular unconformity between the Quaternary and underlying Paleocene sediments (A), along with triangular facets (C) are present on the southern margin of the basin. The Upper Devonian Liuling Formation is overlapped by Member 1 of the Upper Cretaceous Shanyang Formation on the northern margin of the basin (B). Three parallel paleomagnetic samples (E) with independent orientations were drilled using a portable gasoline-powered drilling machine from each stratigraphic level. Drilling cores were orientated *in situ* by using both magnetic and solar compasses (D).

Fig. S2. The bedding attitude and the GPS information acquired by using the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) were applied to calculate the true thickness between different sites (e.g., site 1 and site 2). The distance (s) from A to B' and the azimuth (θ) can be calculated from the GPS information of site 1 and site 2.

Fig. S3. Hysteresis loops (A–C) and stepwise thermal demagnetization of the three orthogonal component isothermal remanent magnetization (IRM) results (D–F) of the representative specimens from the Dongbeigou and Niupanggou sections. The hysteresis loops were corrected by the 70% high field linear correction.

Fig. S4. Orthogonal projection of representative progressive thermal demagnetization in stratigraphic coordinates and the temperature dependence of normalized remanence of the Dongbeigou section. The solid circles (and open squares) represent the horizontal (and vertical) planes. The numbers on the Zijderveld plots refer to the demagnetization temperatures. NRM is the natural remanent magnetization.

Fig. S5. Orthogonal projection of representative progressive thermal demagnetization in stratigraphic coordinates and the temperature dependence of normalized remanence of the Niupanggou section. The solid circles (and open squares) represent the horizontal (and vertical) planes. The numbers on the Zijderveld plots refer to the demagnetization temperatures. NRM is the natural remanent magnetization.

Fig. S6. Orthogonal projection of representative progressive thermal demagnetization in stratigraphic coordinates and the temperature dependence of normalized remanence of the Sigou section. The solid circles (and open squares) represent the horizontal (and vertical) planes. The numbers on the Zijderveld plots refer to the demagnetization temperatures. NRM is the natural remanent magnetization.

- **Fig. S7.** Lithostratigraphic and magnetostratigraphic correlations among the Sigou (A-C), Niupanggou (E-G), Juanlingcao (I-K), and Dongbeigou sections (L-N). Several key marker layers characterized by lithological indicators (e.g., boundary conglomerate) and polarity transitions can be used to establish the correlations. As a result, the astronomical time scale (ATS) of the Sigou section (D) can be applied to estimate the ages of the dinosaur fossils in the Niupanggou section (H). VGP latitudes are for sample ChRM directions converted to virtual geomagnetic poles. Positive (northerly) and negative (southerly) VGP latitudes correspond to normal and reverse polarity, delineated in the polarity column by filled and open bars, respectively. Green open circles are accepted sample data with MAD values of 15° or less (Tables S5–S8). GPTS is the geomagnetic polarity timescale (GPTS 2020) (17).

Fig. S8. Thickness versus age plot for the Juanlingcao section based on correlation of the magnetostratigraphy with the geomagnetic polarity timescale (GPTS 2020) (17). We propose that polarity N5 corresponds to chron C32n.1n (71.449–71.689 Ma). However, we cannot completely rule out the possibility that the lower part of the polarity N5 (0–70 m) corresponds to an older positive chron (e.g., C32n.2n).

Fig. S9. Equal area projections and Zijderveld plots of progressive thermal demagnetization presented in stratigraphic coordinates of the conglomerate specimens from the Dongbeigou section.

The solid circles (and open squares) represent the horizontal (and vertical) planes. Blue (and Green) arrows indicate ChRM declination (and inclination) using a least-squares linear fit using principal-component analysis. ChRM was not isolated from the specimens SYDBG4g-1-1 (A) and SYDBG4g-1-2 (B). Numbers on the Zijderveld plots refer to the demagnetization temperatures. NRM is the natural remanent magnetization. Zijderveld plots are in stratigraphic coordinates. The samples' name follows the same rule (e.g., SYDBG4g-2-1, "SYDBG4g" means the conglomerate sample was drilled from the fourth site of the Dongbeigou section in the Shanyang Basin, "2" refers to the second conglomerate of the fourth site, and "1" refers to the first specimen from the second conglomerate).

Fig. S10. Equal-area projection of declinations and inclinations of the normal and reversal polarity ChRMs from the Dongbeigou section (A) and Sigou sections (C) for the reversals test. Filled (and open) circles plot on the lower (and upper) hemisphere. Fisher statistics and means (solid triangle) and $\alpha 95$ s confidence ellipses are shown. (B, D) The distribution of Watson's V (V_{ω}) for simulated Fisher distributions. The blue dashed line is the upper bound for the smallest 95% of the V_{ω} s calculated for the simulations (V_{crit}). The red solid vertical line is the V_{ω} calculated for the two data sets (the normal and reverse polarity ChRMs). V_{ω} value is less than the V_{crit} value indicating the Fisher mean directions of the normal and reversal polarities are antipodal.

Fig. S11. Equal-area projection of declinations and inclinations of the normal and reverse polarity ChRMs from the Niupanggou (A) and Juanlingcao sections (C) for the reversals test. Notes refer to Figure S10.

Fig. S12. Cumulative distributions of Cartesian coordinates of the bootstrapped means from the data from the four sections. The reverse polarity mode has been flipped to its antipode. The intervals containing 95% of each set of components also are drawn (vertical lines). Given that the confidence bounds from the two data sets overlap in all three components from the Sigou sections

(A–C) and Dongbeigou (D–F) , the means of the reverse and normal modes cannot be distinguished at a 95% confidence level; they pass the bootstrap reversals test. However, the confidence intervals for the different data sets overlap for X and Z components, but not for Y component in the Niupanggou section (J–L), and they overlap for Y component, but not for X and Z components in the Juanlingcao section (G–I).

Fig. S13. Cyclostratigraphic analysis of the Sigou section from the Shanyang Basin. The black curve in (A) represents the high-resolution magnetic susceptibility (MS) data. The red curve in (A) represents 100-kyr short eccentricity cycles. The interpreted 100-kyr eccentricity cycles were extracted with Gaussian bandpass filters using the free software Analyseries 2.0.8 (14). The blue, red, and green curves indicate 99%, 95%, and 90% confidence limits. The MS series was divided into four parts, 16.0–80.0 m (B), 80.0–160.0 m (C), 165.0–242.0 m (D), and 245.0–316.5 m (E) for spectral analysis based on variation in sediment accumulation rate. As we haven't collected samples from two intervals (160.0–165.0 m, 242.0–245.0 m) because of the conglomerate interlayers and dense vegetation, there is no MS data of these two intervals. However, we can make reasonable estimates near the intervals according to the lithology and cycle characteristics.

Fig. S14. More than 1000 dinosaur eggshells were collected from 43 stratigraphic levels of the Niupanggou section near the Niupanggou village. The first stratigraphic level (Level 1) is within the Juanlingcao section. The lithology and the thickness of the stratigraphic levels containing fossils refer to Fig. S7 and Table S10, respectively. The three-dimension map of the Niupanggou section (A) is from Google map (<https://www.google.com/maps>). GPTS is the geomagnetic polarity timescale (GPTS 2020) (17).

Fig. S15. Two incomplete dinosaur eggs of *Macroolithus yaotunensis* (IVPP V31159) (A) were collected from the outcrop (B) of the Niupanggou section after application of consolidant (C). Dinosaur eggs (D, SYD20160502-1; E, SYD20160502-2) of *Macroolithus yaotunensis* were found by local farmers in Juanling country in Shanyang County.

Fig. S16. Pictures of the dinosaur eggshells discovered in the Niupanggou section. The sharp corners, well-preserved surface ornamentations, and the nonuniform size of the eggshells robustly prove they are buried *in situ*. Each square scale is 1 cm × 1 cm.

Fig. S17. Well-preserved sharp corners and surface ornamentations of *Macroolithus yaotunensis*.

Fig. S18. Radial sections of *Elongatoolithus elongatus* from the Shanyang Basin.

Fig. S19. Radial sections of *Macroolithus yaotunensis* from the Shanyang Basin.

Fig. S20. Radial sections of *Stromatoolithus pinglingensis* from the Shanyang Basin. The photos were taken under the normal light (upper) and the orthogonal polarized light (lower), respectively.

Fig. S21. Radial sections of *Shanyangoolithus shanyangensis* (a turtle egg) from the Shanyang Basin.

Table S1. GPS information of the sampling sites in the Juanlingcao section.

Site	E. Long. (°)	N. Lat. (°)	Height (m)	Bedding Dec. (°)	Bedding Inc. (°)	Distance (m)	Azimuth (°)	Thickness (m)
SYTJG1-1	109.995023	33.524943	860	155	22	—	—	—
SYTJG2-1	109.994829	33.524519	863	155	22	39.44	199	13.41
SYTJG3-1	109.995408	33.523468	877	155	22	114.60	158	55.85
SYTJG4-1	109.995554	33.516524	840	197	14	803.10	175	246.80
SYTJG5-1	109.994317	33.515984	836	225	20	179.50	254	19.89
SYTJG6-1	109.999194	33.511097	858	177	7	340.60	181	105.63
SYJLC7-1	109.991537	33.511186	864	260	12	293.50	233	25.87
SYJLC2-1	109.990261	33.510647	884	210	20	133.60	242	45.21
SYJLC3-1	109.989743	33.510179	885	205	18	68.20	235	22.09
SYJLC4-1	109.990034	33.509353	890	205	18	74.90	165	22.49
SYJLC5-1	109.989899	33.208901	888	205	18	69.50	185	18.28
SYJLC6-1	109.989587	33.508421	894	205	18	50.10	208	21.17
SYJLC7-1	109.988940	33.508302	889	205	18	67.40	253	9.18
SYJLC8-1	109.988640	33.507932	887	205	18	55.50	214	15.04
SYJLC9-1	109.987291	33.505615	872	205	18	184.90	206	42.86
SYJLC10-1	109.986995	33.505465	876	200	15	36.40	234	13.70
SYJLC11-1	109.986868	33.505317	893	210	23	16.00	188	19.70
SYJLC12-1	109.986730	33.504981	903	200	22	44.50	195	26.07
SYJLC13-1	109.986234	33.504536	900	190	22	66.50	229	19.01
SYJLC14-1	109.986373	33.504492	908	185	22	7.72	92	7.01
SYJLC15-1	109.991022	33.502936	910	185	22	36.30	199	15.05
SYJLC16-1	109.991022	33.504258	914	180	23	29.30	230	11.44
SYJLC17-1	109.980739	33.516311	916	170	24	43.00	186	18.54
SYJLC18-1	109.986026	33.503751	918	170	24	0.00	0	1.83
SYJLC19-1	109.986015	33.503649	922	170	24	17.30	153	10.38
SYJLC20-1	109.986113	33.503106	926	170	24	51.70	169	24.68
SYJLC21-1	109.986391	33.502704	939	160	24	54.30	150	32.63
SYJLC22-1	109.986406	33.502258	944	160	24	45.60	186	21.24
SYJLC23-1	109.986332	33.501984	946	160	24	22.40	179	10.44
SYJLC24-1	109.987166	33.501630	945	160	24	79.60	129	26.84
SYJLC25-1	109.985815	33.500874	956	160	24	137.30	239	20.70
SYJLC26-1	109.985525	33.500552	960	145	25	49.80	200	19.14
SYJLC27-1	109.985398	33.500118	968	145	25	71.50	217	16.59

Table S2. GPS information of the sampling sites in the Niupanggou section.

Site	E. Long. (°)	N. Lat. (°)	Height (m)	Bedding Dec. (°)	Bedding Inc. (°)	Distance (m)	Azimuth (°)	Thickness (m)
SYJLG1-1	110.003511	33.50656	807	232	10			
SYJLG2-1	110.002411	33.50605	822	250	17	117.00	241	34.41
SYJLG3-1	110.000116	33.50516	816	250	17	235.70	245	62.91
SYJLG4-1	110.000523	33.50426	871	250	17	106.90	159	52.05
SYJLG5-1	110.000142	33.50382	877	250	17	57.50	214	19.34
SYJLG6-1	109.999019	33.50309	841	250	17	131.00	232	2.00
SYJLGKPB	110.003295	33.50064	841	250	17	119.80	222	30.93
SYJLG7-1	109.999979	33.50179	843	250	17	168.00	150	-6.62
SYJLG8-1	109.998580	33.50107	847	245	13	149.00	237	46.34
SYJLG10-1	109.998174	33.50004	871	245	13	120.20	198	41.83
SYJLG11-1	109.998031	33.49993	874	245	13	19.40	222	6.94
SYJLG12-1	109.997750	33.49958	899	228	13	46.50	213	33.23

Table S3. GPS information of the sampling sites in the Dongbeigou section.

Site	E. Long. (°)	N. Lat. (°)	Height (m)	Bedding Dec. (°)	Bedding Inc. (°)	Distance (m)	Azimuth (°)	Thickness (m)
SYDBG1-1	109.977861	33.533885	891.05	163	19			
SYDBG2-1	109.977875	33.533807	890.62	163	19	8.77	171	2.42
SYDBG3-1	109.977704	33.532741	886.88	190	19	119.8	188	31.89
SYDBG4-1	109.978190	33.531516	875.09	200	20	143.6	162	30.09
SYDBG5-1	109.979107	33.530545	853.48	200	20	137.6	142	4.35
SYDBG6-1	109.979535	33.529961	844.66	200	20	76.12	148	7.88
SYDBG7-1	109.981246	33.528550	822.09	200	20	223.39	135	10.48
SYDBG8-1	109.980909	33.528037	819.38	200	20	65.28	209	19.52
SYDBG9-1	109.981079	33.527912	818.54	200	20	21.09	131	1.82
SYDBG10-1	109.981829	33.527529	815.9	210	17	81.63	121	2.9
SYDBG12-1	109.978553	33.519220	777.15	195	14	975.44	198	241.56
SYDBG11-1	109.977840	33.519619	792.24	195	14	79.73	304	8.46
SYDBG13-1	109.977445	33.518625	784.2	225	25	116.74	198	20.9
SYBGK1-1	109.979417	33.516276	780.98	174	19	319.02	145	59.39
SYBGK2-1	33.516272	109.979387	781.71	174	19	2.78	252	0.88
SYBGK3-1	33.516213	109.979241	780.68	174	19	15.14	244	0.72
SYBGK4-1	33.516131	109.979065	780.75	200	13	18.77	241	2.46
SYBGK5-1	33.516215	109.979072	784.56	200	13	9.23	4	1.72
SYBGK6-1	33.516055	109.978864	782.4	200	13	26.4	227	3.18
SYBGK7-1	33.516027	109.978558	785.03	200	13	28.6	264	5.41
SYBGK8-1	33.515835	109.978315	780.16	200	13	31.26	227	1.55
SYBGK9-1	33.515929	109.978241	783.16	200	13	12.48	327	1.24
SYBGK10-1	33.515662	109.977025	773.77	200	13	117.18	255	5.93
SYBGK11-1	33.515671	109.977075	775.96	200	13	4.92	75	1.5
SYBGK12-1	33.515645	109.977701	783.19	200	13	58.36	93	3.11
SYLJC1-1	33.515260	109.978622	779.81	172	13	95.78	117	-0.85
SYLJC19-1	33.512993	109.979069	807.44	174	18	255.68	171	83.78

Table S4. GPS information of the sampling sites in the Sigou section.

Site	E. Long. (°)	N. Lat. (°)	Height (m)	Bedding Dec. (°)	Bedding Inc. (°)	Distance (m)	Azimuth (°)	Thickness (m)
SYSG_Start	33.521436	109.945568	722.24	163	20			
SYSG_KPB	33.514611	109.946088	760.21	155	15	761.45	176	290.01
SYSG_end	33.509958	109.948065	783.59	125	11	549.52	161	164.52

Table S5. Paleomagnetic results from principal component analysis of the Sigou specimens.

No.	Specimen	H (m)	D_Geog.	I_Geog.	D_Strat.	I_Strat.	points	N	MAD	VGP_Plon.	VGP_Plat.
234	SYSG617-1	316.66	12.80	33.30	20.10	36.80	H-M	6	10.50	231	67.9
233	SYSG615-3	316.00	334.80	43.00	341.50	52.20	L-Q	6	12.40	22.5	74.5
232	SYSG609-1	313.66	346.70	31.20	352.10	39.00	C-J	8	8.50	323.3	76.6
231	SYSG602-1	311.33	4.00	32.50	10.80	37.60	F-M	8	3.60	249.7	74.3
230	SYSG601-1	310.66	46.30	15.80	48.60	12.00	K-O	5	3.60	220.2	37.4
229	SYSG597-1	309.33	23.20	5.20	24.10	5.40	G-N	8	4.20	248.7	51.9
228	SYSG595-2	308.66	19.80	43.20	29.20	43.20	G-N	8	7.30	210.5	63.3
227	SYSG591-1	305.66	1.20	44.50	11.10	47.70	J-P	7	6.70	223.4	79.4
226	SYSG589-1	305.00	1.00	50.40	17.20	65.40	E-IK-NW	9	6.50	147.6	70.9
225	SYSG587-1	304.33	50.50	51.90	74.10	52.80	E-IK-NW	9	6.80	177.5	29.6
224	SYSG585-1	303.66	35.60	58.10	67.00	62.60	K-O	5	11.90	167.4	38.1
223	SYSG581-1	302.33	64.60	29.40	74.40	28.00	D-IK-M	9	5.80	195.7	21
222	SYSG579-2	301.66	21.70	37.90	35.50	48.70	D-IK-M	9	6.10	197.5	59.7
221	SYSG565-2	297.00	12.40	50.20	32.70	62.70	I-P	8	6.30	167.6	62.6
220	SYSG563-3	296.00	3.50	39.20	11.80	51.90	I-N	6	3.20	202.4	80.1
219	SYSG561-1	295.33	346.30	28.40	349.40	46.00	G-N	8	10.40	348.9	79
218	SYSG559-2	294.66	35.10	35.70	48.80	42.80	H-N	7	4.10	198.3	46.9
217	SYSG557-3	294.00	18.50	48.80	38.90	59.70	H-N	7	3.70	175.7	58.4
216	SYSG555-1	293.33	352.60	-17.00	351.80	0.20	T-W	4	5.50	304.7	55.7
215	SYSG551-1	292.00	49.60	45.70	68.80	47.60	F-N	9	5.60	184.6	32
214	SYSG549-2	291.00	357.60	5.80	359.00	19.60	Q-U	5	4.20	292.5	66.6
213	SYSG547-1	290.33	343.60	28.10	345.30	42.90	Q-U	5	2.40	350	74.6
212	SYSG545-2	289.00	3.90	31.30	10.10	44.10	P-V	7	3.30	238.5	78.4

211	SYSG543-1	288.00	18.80	38.80	29.80	48.60	H-N	7	5.50	200.7	64.4
210	SYSG541-2	286.00	16.40	17.00	20.70	27.90	R-V	5	10.40	239.9	63.6
209	SYSG539-1	283.00	5.80	58.60	26.60	70.10	K-N	4	10.20	144.2	62.2
208	SYSG537-3	282.00	66.20	49.30	82.80	46.80	F-M	8	15.10	179.3	20.6
207	SYSG535-2	281.00	22.80	-0.20	23.70	9.80	P-V	7	3.30	247.2	53.9
206	SYSG533-2	280.00	34.60	26.00	42.20	32.80	G-N	8	6.80	211.8	49.2
205	SYSG531-1	279.33	30.40	56.80	54.50	62.80	H-L	5	5.30	168.9	47.1
204	SYSG529-1	278.50	0.50	25.70	5.00	39.00	G-M	7	6.00	267.7	77.7
203	SYSG527-1	277.50	50.10	55.20	72.30	56.20	H-M	6	5.40	174.5	32.2
202	SYSG525-2	276.75	20.50	13.30	24.20	23.60	H-M	6	3.40	238.1	59.4
201	SYSG523-3	276.25	14.90	36.70	24.50	47.40	H-M	6	9.10	206.7	68.5
200	SYSG521-2	275.75	9.70	49.70	24.30	61.00	H-M	6	1.70	168.8	69.1
199	SYSG519-1	275.25	27.60	37.80	39.10	45.70	G-M	7	5.10	200.1	55.9
198	SYSG517-3	274.66	7.50	51.40	22.60	63.00	I-M	5	5.80	161.2	69.4
197	SYSG513-3	273.00	348.20	68.80	15.00	82.60	J-M	4	6.00	115.5	47.5
196	SYSG511-1	272.00	30.40	42.70	44.40	49.70	I-N	6	9.60	192.1	52.5
195	SYSG510-1	271.50	62.90	46.70	78.40	45.30	J-O	6	5.20	182.4	23.5
194	SYSG509-2	256.33	351.20	36.30	355.70	50.60	J-O	6	4.50	350.3	85.8
193	SYSG507-3	255.66	11.70	-0.10	12.60	11.90	J-O	6	4.20	264.2	60.1
192	SYSG501-2	236.66	248.20	-25.10	254.90	-23.30	I-O	7	6.40	17.9	-19.2
191	SYSG499-3	236.00	172.90	-38.60	178.30	-52.60	S-W	5	3.10	187.9	-88.5
190	SYSG496-2	234.33	185.40	-43.50	195.80	-55.80	H-M	6	11.10	3.2	-76.8
189	SYSG493-2	233.33	169.60	-18.60	171.50	-33.10	J-M	4	9.10	138.3	-72.8
188	SYSG491-3	232.66	175.00	-33.30	179.90	-47.20	I-M	5	7.00	111	-84.9
187	SYSG488-2	231.66	162.20	-56.70	167.50	-71.50	L-Q	6	4.90	273	-65.7
186	SYSG487-1	231.33	166.70	-14.80	168.00	-29.40	L-Q	6	3.50	144.3	-69.2

185	SYSG486-1	230.66	171.10	-52.80	180.20	-66.90	H-M	6	8.50	290.5	-74
184	SYSG484-2	230.00	161.00	-48.20	163.90	-63.10	I-O	7	3.60	246.4	-73.3
183	SYSG483-3	229.66	191.00	-32.70	198.70	-44.30	H-O	8	5.00	39.9	-72.2
182	SYSG482-2	229.33	187.50	-57.60	207.90	-68.80	H-O	8	5.60	328.6	-62.6
181	SYSG481-3	229.00	142.60	-26.30	140.20	-40.90	G-M	7	11.10	194.4	-53.8
180	SYSG480-2	228.66	154.50	-38.50	154.40	-53.50	H-M	6	5.70	208.6	-68.8
179	SYSG479-2	228.33	180.40	-67.90	216.30	-79.40	I-M	5	14.10	308.4	-48.8
178	SYSG478-3	228.00	175.00	-23.80	178.30	-37.80	H-M	6	7.10	117.4	-77.6
177	SYSG476-2	227.33	179.00	-42.40	187.20	-55.70	F-M	8	8.50	353.1	-83.5
176	SYSG475-3	227.00	178.90	-64.60	205.20	-76.90	F-M	8	6.20	308.2	-55
175	SYSG474-1	226.66	168.60	48.40	165.00	-25.50	Q-V	6	15.00	147.8	-65.7
174	SYSG473-3	226.33	192.00	-9.00	194.50	-20.80	R-V	5	4.90	76.3	-63.7
173	SYSG472-1	226.00	179.90	-52.60	193.00	-65.50	H-L	5	2.50	320.8	-72.8
172	SYSG471-1	225.66	180.50	-27.40	185.20	-40.70	H-M	6	7.70	84.6	-78.8
171	SYSG469-1	225.00	181.80	-36.70	188.90	-49.70	G-M	7	6.70	39.1	-81.9
170	SYSG462-3	222.33	164.50	-17.60	165.80	-32.40	P-V	7	4.60	152.2	-69.6
169	SYSG461-3	222.00	226.10	-34.40	236.90	-38.00	K-P	6	13.60	18.3	-38.7
168	SYSG460-2	221.66	175.10	-52.30	186.10	-65.90	H-O	8	9.80	305.5	-74.6
167	SYSG457-1	220.66	131.50	-18.40	128.50	-32.00	T-W	4	11.10	193.9	-41.3
166	SYSG454-1	200.00	200.00	-44.00	210.90	-56.00	H-M	6	13.00	4.3	-64.6
165	SYSG452-1	199.33	188.50	-36.10	194.10	-49.90	G-L	6	5.30	29.4	-77.7
164	SYSG451-1	199.00	203.90	-49.00	218.50	-60.10	I-N	6	8.80	354.8	-58.7
163	SYSG449-1	198.33	165.70	-59.10	163.60	-74.10	I-O	7	3.40	273.2	-61.1
162	SYSG448-1	198.00	181.70	-67.00	203.60	-80.90	K-P	6	5.30	300.8	-49.4
161	SYSG447-1	197.66	198.50	-35.80	206.10	-48.20	H-P	9	5.10	23.8	-67.4
160	SYSG446-1	197.33	181.50	-16.80	183.20	-31.30	I-P	8	3.00	99.4	-73.2

159	SYSG445-3	197.00	162.70	-56.20	159.00	-71.10	L-U	10	5.70	263	-63.5
158	SYSG444-1	196.66	189.60	-16.90	192.20	-30.70	M-OQR	5	8.90	74.1	-69.8
157	SYSG443-1	196.33	175.40	-22.30	176.60	-37.20	H-N	7	9.70	124.2	-76.9
156	SYSG442-1	196.00	214.20	-41.50	226.60	-50.70	I-O	7	9.30	9.8	-51
155	SYSG441-2	195.66	165.20	-58.40	162.80	-73.40	G-M	7	7.90	271.3	-61.9
154	SYSG440-3	195.33	176.60	-16.20	177.60	-31.00	H-M	6	2.90	117.9	-73.1
153	SYSG439-1	195.00	183.70	-29.90	187.10	-44.20	H-L	5	5.70	69	-80.2
152	SYSG437-2	194.33	226.70	-43.00	241.10	-49.20	G-L	6	5.30	6.1	-38.7
151	SYSG436-3	194.00	156.2	-36.6	153.9	-51.4	E-MV	10	29.4	203.5	-68.1
150	SYSG433-2	192.33	60.6	25.2	68.6	31.6	G-LU	7	7.1	196.6	26.9
149	SYSG429-3	190.33	310.2	59.4	275.5	73.8	L-PRSW	8	14.8	74.2	31.2
148	SYSG423-1	186.66	37.50	48.80	62.30	57.30	R-U	4	5.30	176.1	40.2
147	SYSG417-2-1	184.00	350.30	59.00	340.60	70.10	I-N	6	6.70	82.2	65.3
146	SYSG415-2	183.33	26.60	15.10	28.20	26.50	R-U	4	9.30	230.5	57.8
145	SYSG411-1-1	179.66	344.60	36.70	343.80	48.70	L-O	4	17.10	8.8	75.7
144	SYSG409-1	179.00	55.50	22.50	61.50	16.20	D-J	7	5.10	209.2	28.2
143	SYSG405-3-1	177.00	345.30	24.00	352.40	37.70	K-O	5	4.20	320.5	75.9
142	SYSG403-2	176.33	7.00	25.80	16.40	33.80	I-N	6	5.50	241.6	69
141	SYSG401-3	175.66	23.30	33.00	35.60	35.70	J-O	6	6.00	214.4	55.6
140	SYSG399-3	175.00	341.00	28.10	348.70	42.60	G-M	7	6.30	341.1	76.8
139	SYSG397-2-1	174.33	2.90	26.40	12.40	35.50	I-O	7	4.80	248.4	72.3
138	SYSG395-2	173.66	358.40	58.70	30.70	66.20	H-M	6	8.40	157.3	62.7
137	SYSG393-1	173.00	351.70	48.40	11.90	59.30	L-O	4	11.80	161.8	78.4
136	SYSG391-3	172.33	344.90	12.20	348.90	26.30	J-N	5	8.70	319.8	67.9
135	SYSG385-3-1	170.33	315.80	34.10	317.20	45.00	I-M	5	4.40	21	52.6
134	SYSG383-1	169.66	352.70	37.30	359.80	44.60	K-P	6	5.80	291.4	82.7

133	SYSG381-1	169.00	13.70	2.90	14.60	7.30	K-N	4	8.50	262.3	57.2
132	SYSG379-1	168.33	15.40	64.40	39.30	66.40	H-M	6	5.80	160.2	57.2
131	SYSG377-2	167.66	47.60	56.60	62.70	53.40	J-P	7	7.90	180.9	38.7
130	SYSG375-3	167.00	292.80	21.60	291.20	32.10	H-K	4	7.60	23.8	26.9
129	SYSG373-2-1	166.33	332.50	32.00	336.20	41.80	S-U	3	13.90	1.9	67.2
128	SYSG365-1	159.00	15.40	16.60	22.20	28.60	Q-U	5	6.10	236.9	62.9
127	SYSG363-3	158.33	7.20	22.80	15.60	36.70	G-M	7	5.50	239.4	71
126	SYSG361-2-1	157.66	8.50	23.80	17.40	37.40	K-MOP	5	8.90	234.8	70.1
125	SYSG357-1	156.33	24.80	56.70	58.20	61.70	D-K	8	7.50	170.4	44.2
124	SYSG355-1	155.66	359.60	49.30	21.50	63.70	K-M	3	16.50	158	69.7
123	SYSG353-1	155.00	325.50	9.60	325.60	29.60	P-V	7	14.90	358.9	54.4
122	SYSG351-3-1	154.33	27.50	19.90	35.80	27.90	G-M	7	5.10	221.2	52.7
121	SYSG349-2	153.66	9.90	17.30	16.70	30.70	S-V	4	10.20	244.4	67.3
120	SYSG347-1	153.00	327.40	65.50	337.30	85.40	LMO-Q	5	13.90	105.3	41.8
119	SYSG345-3	152.33	46.90	43.10	65.80	42.70	J-MO-Q	7	6.40	190.1	32.8
118	SYSG343-1	151.66	46.00	60.70	80.10	57.80	Q-V	6	10.70	170.1	27.1
117	SYSG339-1	150.33	48.90	17.60	55.50	18.60	G-L	6	2.30	211.8	33.9
116	SYSG337-2	149.66	328.20	-16.00	328.10	3.90	T-W	4	7.20	340.2	46.6
115	SYSG335-3	149.00	352.30	26.90	359.70	44.10	K-Q	7	8.10	292	82.3
114	SYSG331-2	142.00	10.60	28.20	21.20	43.50	F-L	7	4.30	218.2	69.9
113	SYSG329-2-1	141.33	335.20	63.70	347.20	84.50	I-M	5	11.50	106.7	44.1
112	SYSG325-1	140.00	1.80	33.50	12.90	50.70	F-M	8	5.10	207.3	78.9
111	SYSG317-3	137.33	43.80	19.60	52.20	24.80	F-M	8	9.30	210.4	38.5
110	SYSG317-3	137.33	75.00	25.60	83.40	19.30	M-R	5	16.20	195.2	10.9
109	SYSG311-1	135.33	8.20	45.50	28.70	60.30	Q-U	5	11.50	172.8	66
108	SYSG305-3	133.33	39.60	36.90	56.70	42.10	T-V	3	8.50	195	40.1

107	SYSG303-1	132.66	317.70	1.70	316.50	22.00	J-M	4	8.00	1.4	44.6
106	SYSG299-2	131.33	18.60	-4.60	19.30	9.80	G-N	8	5.50	253.6	56.3
105	SYSG291-1	127.00	18.00	32.70	28.90	44.70	K-Q	7	14.40	208.3	64
104	SYSG289-3	126.00	357.80	40.70	7.30	56.70	E-L	8	6.10	165.5	83
103	SYSG287-1	125.33	322.60	64.00	299.00	80.80	M-Q	5	14.00	89.2	40.5
102	SYSG285-3	124.66	343.00	45.00	347.50	62.70	I-O	7	11.30	71.2	75.6
101	SYSG283-3	124.00	356.60	25.70	1.50	42.20	J-P	7	7.60	281.4	80.8
100	SYSG281-1	122.66	350.00	36.20	355.50	53.40	H-O	8	8.30	28.1	86.2
99	SYSG279-2	122.00	6.80	9.30	9.80	24.40	P-V	7	9.70	264.4	67.4
98	SYSG247-3	121.33	3.60	21.90	8.40	40.30	P-V	7	4.40	252.8	77.1
97	SYSG245-1	120.00	14.20	-3.40	15.10	13.70	S-V	4	11.20	258.9	60
96	SYSG243-1	119.33	24.00	-11.80	23.00	3.50	Q-V	6	13.70	251	51.6
95	SYSG237-1	117.33	52.30	38.50	69.30	42.80	G-N	8	11.50	188.5	30
94	SYSG231-3	114.00	343.00	-4.70	343.00	15.30	K-T	10	14.20	325.2	59.9
93	SYSG229-3	113.33	12.10	22.30	18.60	39.30	F-N	9	5.80	229.7	70.1
92	SYSG227-2	112.66	15.60	17.90	21.30	34.30	E-L	8	7.70	232.3	66
91	SYSG225-2	112.00	15.70	19.60	21.90	35.90	E-K	7	10.10	229.4	66.3
90	SYSG221-1	110.66	17.60	57.50	50.40	70.70	I-P	8	8.40	152.6	49.2
89	SYSG217-1	109.33	297.70	26.30	287.70	39.20	H-N	7	8.20	30.2	26.3
88	SYSG215-3	108.66	0.70	22.00	4.80	40.90	H-N	7	6.00	266.1	79.1
87	SYSG213-3	108.00	320.00	21.10	314.90	39.20	Q-U	5	8.60	16	48.9
86	SYSG209-1-1	106.66	331.50	18.10	329.10	37.60	P-V	7	11.00	3.5	60
85	SYSG207-1	106.00	209.00	-41.50	227.10	-53.20	R-U	4	10.20	6.1	-51.1
84	SYSG203-2	104.00	10.00	59.00	42.50	74.30	J-P	7	10.70	142.1	51.5
83	SYSG201-1	103.33	353.40	42.00	359.20	61.50	L-P	5	8.40	106.3	80.8
82	SYSG197B-1	101.33	327.60	31.00	322.20	50.10	G-M	7	6.80	25.8	58.1

81	SYSG197A-1	101.00	291.60	26.90	280.80	38.00	G-M	7	5.80	32.8	20.3
80	SYSG197-3	99.33	357.30	4.00	358.60	23.30	L-T	9	8.10	293.8	68.6
79	SYSG193-3	97.66	7.10	25.40	13.50	43.30	K-R	8	7.20	231.6	75.6
78	SYSG191-1	97.00	16.10	32.00	26.60	47.80	M-R	6	11.40	204.3	66.8
77	SYSG189-1	96.33	28.60	20.50	36.40	33.60	G-LN-P	9	5.70	215.7	54.2
76	SYSG185-2	95.00	357.60	25.20	1.70	44.40	J-O	6	7.90	278.3	82.4
75	SYSG183-1	94.33	350.80	44.00	355.70	63.70	T-X	5	3.80	95.7	77.7
74	SYSG181-1	93.66	41.00	30.30	53.70	39.10	N-S	6	9.80	199.1	41.7
73	SYSG179-3	93.00	4.60	57.10	29.80	74.10	G-M	7	5.50	136.8	56.9
72	SYSG177-3	92.33	3.20	34.00	11.00	52.30	F-M	8	3.90	200.7	80.8
71	SYSG175-3	91.66	9.40	21.70	15.20	39.20	H-N	7	6.40	236.3	72.5
70	SYSG169-1	89.66	3.20	40.00	13.20	58.20	I-O	7	6.80	169.4	78.1
69	SYSG166A-1	88.33	0.80	27.30	6.00	46.10	G-M	7	1.70	247.9	82
68	SYSG165-1	87.66	12.80	17.90	18.20	34.80	L-P	5	8.60	236.9	68.3
67	SYSG163-2-1	87.00	25.60	36.80	40.20	49.90	I-O	7	11.30	193.5	56
66	SYSG159-3	85.66	21.40	17.90	27.80	33.00	E-N	10	4.90	225	60.7
65	SYSG157-1-1	85.00	30.80	15.50	37.00	28.20	I-O	7	6.30	219.8	51.8
64	SYSG153-3-2	83.66	22.00	17.70	28.40	32.60	L-Q	6	5.60	224.7	60.1
63	SYSG151-1	83.00	47.00	23.10	56.50	30.50	U-Y	5	4.70	204	36.7
62	SYSG149-1	81.66	5.70	-1.00	6.90	17.40	U-WY	4	9.30	273.9	64.6
61	SYSG147-3	81.00	15.90	35.10	27.80	50.80	G-N	8	5.50	197.2	66.5
60	SYSG141-3-1	79.00	339.10	51.70	335.30	71.60	K-N	4	4.00	80.9	61.5
59	SYSG135-1-1	77.00	33.60	46.00	55.60	55.80	F-N	9	6.50	179.9	45
58	SYSG133-2-1	76.33	7.80	18.00	12.50	35.80	L-S	8	4.10	247.7	72.4
57	SYSG131-3-1	75.66	35.90	27.60	47.10	38.20	L-S	8	9.50	203.7	46.9
56	SYSG127-2	74.33	325.10	21.70	321.00	40.60	U-X	4	16.90	13.5	54.4

55	SYSG123-1	73.00	13.20	41.60	27.70	57.70	T-X	5	7.50	179.8	67.1
54	SYSG121-1	72.33	158.30	-49.40	154.40	-69.30	S-W	5	6.90	254.5	-63.3
53	SYSG115-1-1	70.33	14.70	1.00	16.60	17.90	U-X	4	6.70	254.1	61.3
52	SYSG113-1-1	69.66	306.20	15.80	300.60	31.30	U-X	4	15.00	18.2	34.5
51	SYSG107-3	67.66	307.10	-6.10	306.70	10.10	T-W	4	8.70	2.3	33
50	SYSG100-3-2	65.33	36.80	62.40	80.00	67.80	J-N	5	3.50	156.8	31.3
49	SYSG97-1-1	64.33	114.10	-14.20	108.20	-26.60	P-S	4	11.30	202.2	-22.7
48	SYSG93-3	63.00	297.00	25.20	287.30	38.00	N-S	6	12.90	29.6	25.6
47	SYSG89-3	61.66	33.60	22.30	42.40	33.90	I-N	6	7.20	210.7	49.4
46	SYSG85-2-2	60.66	15.70	-1.10	17.10	15.60	RT-V	4	7.10	254.4	60
45	SYSG83-3-1	60.00	352.90	37.30	357.50	56.90	J-O	6	2.50	83.7	85.5
44	SYSG80-4	58.66	129.80	-28.50	120.70	-44.50	L-O	4	12.10	208.5	-38.7
43	SYSG79A-1	56.33	120.50	-1.90	118.20	-16.50	L-R	7	6.20	191.1	-28.1
42	SYSG77-1	55.33	170.30	-27.80	172.50	-47.60	K-N	4	14.20	165.2	-82
41	SYSG75-3	54.66	254.20	-6.00	256.20	-5.20	H-M	6	9.80	25.5	-12.9
40	SYSG71-1	52.66	237.50	-28.50	249.10	-31.90	I-N	6	11.90	16.2	-26.6
39	SYSG65-1	50.66	122.70	-46.30	102.10	-59.20	Q-T	4	10.10	230.8	-29.2
38	SYSG63-2-2	50.00	319.20	9.20	316.40	27.40	P-S	4	4.20	5.1	46.3
37	SYSG55-2	47.33	3.60	18.80	7.70	37.30	T-V	3	8.00	259.7	75.6
36	SYSG53-3-1	46.66	334.50	67.10	292.40	85.70	S-V	4	12.40	100.2	36.4
35	SYSG49-2-2	45.33	64.10	32.80	77.30	33.60	K-N	4	7.40	190.9	20.4
34	SYSG45-2-1	44.00	289.90	9.60	285.30	21.00	I-M	5	8.80	20.9	18.7
33	SYSG37-2-2	41.33	354.20	68.80	61.00	85.90	H-M	6	8.70	119	37.1
32	SYSG33-1-1	40.00	24.90	40.60	41.70	53.60	F-IK-M	7	5.50	187	55.6
31	SYSG31-1-1	39.33	25.70	39.70	42.10	52.60	H-N	7	4.40	188.5	55.1
30	SYSG29-3-1	38.66	15.50	32.50	26.10	48.50	H-O	8	8.10	203.2	67.4

29	SYSG27-3-1	38.00	10.80	40.90	24.10	57.60	G-N	8	4.70	179.4	70
28	SYSG25-3	37.33	5.90	27.30	12.50	45.40	J-U	12	4.50	228.2	77.3
27	SYSG23-3-1	36.66	18.40	41.80	34.60	56.50	G-P	10	6.20	182.8	61.7
26	SYSG19-1-1	35.33	53.50	15.00	59.80	20.70	T-W	4	14.30	207.9	31
25	SYSG17-2	34.66	21.50	27.20	31.10	41.90	J-P	7	6.90	210.8	61.3
24	SYSG15-2	34.00	13.20	26.20	21.00	42.90	LMO-S	7	11.80	219.6	69.8
23	SYSG13-1-1	33.33	354.10	32.40	358.20	51.80	MNP-SUV	8	10.70	345.2	88.1
22	SYSG09-2-2	32.00	10.50	61.50	49.40	76.10	PR-U	5	3.70	139.8	47.3
21	SYSG07-1-1	32.00	327.00	51.60	312.70	70.20	P-T	5	11.10	66.8	51.1
20	SYSG03-1	30.66	20.90	29.60	31.40	44.30	G-N	8	5.70	207	61.8
19	SYSG01-2	30.00	353.40	37.50	358.20	57.00	G-M	7	5.90	90.8	85.7
18	SYSG37-1	29.00	17.50	33.60	28.90	49.00	H-O	8	3.20	200.4	65.2
17	SYSG19-1	23.00	335.90	12.00	334.80	31.80	P-V	7	3.70	350.5	62.1
16	SYSG12-1	20.66	346.00	33.10	346.00	33.10	O-W	8	7.10	332.5	70.1
15	SYSGB03-2	15.00	310.10	6.30	310.30	17.30	Q-V	6	7.10	3.4	38.2
14	SYSGB05-1	14.34	336.90	13.80	338.90	23.00	R-U	4	11.10	336.8	61.1
13	SYSGB11-1	12.34	13.30	15.80	18.20	32.70	O-U	7	5.40	239.4	67.4
12	SYSGB15-3	11.00	9.90	28.00	17.60	45.30	H-N	7	5.70	219.1	73.4
11	SYSGB17-2-1	10.34	24.30	4.40	27.20	19.10	P-U	6	9.50	237.2	55.6
10	SYSGB21-1-1	9.00	19.00	32.60	30.30	47.70	J-P	7	7.60	202.1	63.7
9	SYSGB23-1-1	8.34	345.00	31.00	345.80	51.00	O-V	8	9.80	15.3	77.9
8	SYSGB25-2-1	7.67	36.00	50.50	62.30	58.90	J-N	5	6.60	173.9	40.6
7	SYSGB27-1-1	7.00	17.80	58.20	52.00	71.20	H-L	5	1.90	151.7	48.2
6	SYSGB29-1-2	6.34	335.80	43.60	331.20	63.40	P-S	4	11.60	55.9	65.1
5	SYSGB31-1	5.67	27.00	39.50	43.50	51.90	G-M	7	6.30	189.2	53.8
4	SYSGB35-3-2	4.34	23.60	35.60	37.20	49.30	H-N	7	6.40	195.7	58.4

3	SYSGB36-3	3.67	14.60	58.60	48.40	72.50	I-U	13	10.20	148	49.7
2	SYSGB41-3	2.00	13.90	-4.20	14.70	12.90	Q-U	5	5.50	259.9	59.8
1	SYSGB45-2	0.34	29.50	39.40	46.20	51.10	H-N	7	3.80	189.4	51.4

Table S6. Paleomagnetic results from principal component analysis of the Dongbeigou specimens.

No.	Specimen	H (m)	D_Geog.	I_Geog.	D_Strat.	I_Strat.	points	N	MAD	VGP_Plon.	VGP_Plat.
137	SYLJC19-4	553.30	306.50	25.10	298.00	36.30	E-IL	6	6.10	23.1	33.9
136	SYLJC18-5	541.03	65.30	33.60	78.00	37.50	R-V	5	13.90	188.2	21.1
135	SYLJC18-3	541.02	137.30	5.50	137.00	-9.00	S-V	4	14.10	173.7	-40.7
134	SYLJC17-5	539.04	140.80	-67.30	90.10	-77.70	R-V	5	10.20	262.4	-30.4
133	SYLJC16-4	537.02	242.00	-49.80	264.60	-53.30	G-M	7	10.50	353	-21.9
132	SYLJC16-1	537.01	133.60	-55.80	106.60	-66.80	G-M	7	10.60	240.4	-35
131	SYLJC13-4	531.14	9.00	-2.80	9.50	14.60	L-T	9	7.50	269.3	62.5
130	SYLJC12-5	523.05	26.90	52.00	47.50	65.40	N-T	7	13.50	163.9	52
129	SYLJC10-3	507.02	54.60	42.30	66.70	47.00	K-N	4	6.30	186	33.5
128	SYLJC8-6	499.06	7.00	14.20	8.30	26.70	N-V	9	8.00	266.8	69.2
127	SYLJC8-3	499.02	21.80	5.50	23.10	16.70	N-TV	8	7.50	244.3	57.2
126	SYLJC6-3	491.02	62.50	31.90	70.90	35.40	E-M	9	9.30	193	26.2
125	SYLJC6-1	491.01	59.80	49.80	75.70	53.00	J-P	7	5.60	176.7	28.5
124	SYLJC5-2	486.01	9.30	23.60	11.70	35.90	R-W	6	6.50	249.6	72.9
123	SYLJC4-5	483.05	9.50	-6.10	9.50	6.30	J-P	7	6.50	271.7	58.4
122	SYLJC4-1	483.01	44.90	-4.10	44.90	3.80	L-R	7	6.60	227.2	37.5
121	SYLJC3-5	473.04	57.40	23.80	63.40	28.60	G-P	10	5.90	201.3	30.4
120	SYLJC3-2	473.01	307.10	0.90	306.20	10.00	O-V	8	11.10	2.6	32.6
119	SYLJC2-6	470.55	338.20	35.30	335.10	47.90	P-W	8	13.30	14.7	68.3
118	SYLJC2-4	470.53	40.30	26.90	46.40	35.10	Q-V	6	7.20	206.9	46.5
117	SYBGK12-6	470.43	0.70	7.40	359.60	19.70	J-N	5	3.80	291	66.6
116	SYLJC1-5	469.55	5.50	8.50	6.30	21.20	K-R	8	10.80	274.2	66.7

115	SYBGK11-4	467.32	31.00	34.50	33.40	47.20	J-N	5	7.00	201.1	61
114	SYBGK11-1	467.25	2.90	35.20	359.10	47.50	M-P	4	10.10	299.2	85.1
113	SYBGK10-5	465.80	13.10	5.10	12.70	18.00	I-P	8	5.40	261.4	63.1
112	SYBGK8-3	458.61	232.80	2.70	233.10	-8.30	R-U	4	14.10	38.7	-32.7
111	SYBGK7-2	457.05	151.50	-53.30	151.50	-53.30	P-TVW	7	12.40	208.9	-66.4
110	SYBGK5-4	448.51	207.00	-18.10	207.70	-31.00	N-V	9	6.20	47.1	-60
109	SYBGK5-3	448.48	191.40	-22.80	190.20	-35.60	G-JL-V	15	3.40	74.1	-73.5
108	SYBGK4-6	446.79	231.80	-41.90	240.10	-52.50	S-V	4	13.00	2.8	-40.5
107	SYBGK2-1	444.46	190.00	-20.40	193.30	-38.50	I-N	6	4.50	61.8	-73.3
106	SYBGK3-4	444.30	231.70	-15.90	238.00	-25.30	O-V	8	10.60	26.4	-33.8
105	SYBGK3-2	444.28	127.70	-36.90	113.60	-48.40	R-U	4	8.80	215.2	-34.2
104	SYBGK2-4	443.58	143.30	-10.50	139.80	-26.50	R-V	5	9.60	181.7	-48.7
103	SYDBG13-184	412.50	214.00	-32.40	207.90	-56.70	M-SU	8	14.40	2.6	-67
102	SYDBG13-183	412.45	130.50	-61.30	94.80	-51.20	R-UX	5	9.80	225.4	-20.5
101	SYDBG13-178	411.40	177.30	-17.90	167.60	-33.30	L-Q	6	5.70	149	-71.1
100	SYDBG13-177	411.36	190.70	-6.30	186.20	-26.50	N-UX	9	9.40	92.4	-69.7
99	SYDBG13-170	410.79	209.60	-42.80	196.20	-66.10	K-N	4	6.90	324.2	-70.8
98	SYDBG13-166	410.61	151.80	-47.20	123.50	-48.40	P-SX	5	6.60	211.2	-42.2
97	SYDBG13-162	409.76	192.60	-32.40	177.90	-51.90	I-MPQ	7	9.60	171.6	-88
96	SYDBG13-163	409.71	206.90	-0.60	205.00	-24.30	G-LX	7	7.00	56.4	-59.2
95	SYDBG13-160	408.96	176.60	-35.30	157.00	-48.80	I-LX	5	7.80	195.3	-70.1
94	SYDBG13-195	407.15	206.70	-31.30	197.50	-54.50	R-Y	8	7.80	9.1	-75.5
93	SYDBG13-135	405.08	220.40	-8.30	219.60	-33.20	L-PT-X	10	14.30	33.4	-51.5
92	SYDBG13-128	404.22	194.40	-36.40	177.60	-56.10	RT-WX	6	15.20	258.8	-86.3
91	SYDBG13-124	403.71	211.10	-3.50	209.30	-27.70	SUW	3	5.70	48.2	-57.5

90	SYDBG13-120	403.66	153.30	-27.50	138.90	-32.40	P-SX	5	13.30	187	-50
89	SYDBG13-121	403.66	219.30	-53.60	208.10	-78.20	O-T	6	7.10	307.3	-52.5
88	SYDBG13-117	402.79	196.60	2.20	194.60	-19.70	O-RUVX	7	5.10	76.8	-63.1
87	SYDBG13-106	400.61	185.60	-14.40	177.90	-32.80	O-TX	7	5.70	117.4	-74.2
86	SYDBG13-99	399.51	213.80	-19.30	210.40	-43.70	F-MX	9	10.40	28.7	-62.5
85	SYDBG13-95	398.53	181.80	-10.50	175.40	-27.90	O-QSUW-	9	4.30	123.7	-70.9
84	SYDBG13-91	397.87	213.70	-33.10	207.20	-57.40	SUWY	4	10.00	0.6	-67.6
83	SYDBG13-89	397.77	192.60	-14.20	185.90	-34.60	G-PX	11	8.50	88.5	-74.6
82	SYDBG13-85	397.04	209.80	3.50	208.80	-20.60	G-LX	7	16.10	54.2	-55.1
81	SYDBG13-82	397.02	233.00	-4.70	234.20	-29.40	G-MX	8	10.10	26.2	-38.3
80	SYDBG13-79	394.52	154.20	-15.00	146.10	-21.60	N-TX	8	11.60	172.3	-51.8
79	SYDBG13-80	394.50	237.60	-22.60	242.10	-46.90	PQS UWYZ	7	3.10	8	-37.2
78	SYDBG13-72	392.96	161.20	-29.50	145.20	-37.50	K-P	6	6.40	186.9	-56.8
77	SYDBG13-71	392.68	143.50	-16.10	135.60	-18.10	Q-SUX	5	15.70	179.8	-42.6
76	SYDBG13-62	391.74	175.40	-12.90	167.80	-28.00	H-NX	8	10.10	143.6	-68.4
75	SYDBG13-58	391.62	160.30	-13.10	152.70	-22.50	O-QSUW	6	8.20	165.3	-56.9
74	SYDBG13-54	390.83	223.30	-1.60	223.20	-26.60	L-PR	6	7.80	35.8	-46.4
73	SYDBG13-37	388.27	169.60	-40.70	145.40	-50.60	I-OX	8	7.90	205.4	-60.8
72	SYDBG13-34	388.22	193.20	-10.20	187.80	-30.90	G-MW	8	9.80	85.5	-71.8
71	SYDBG13-35	388.21	211.60	-36.80	202.70	-60.70	L-P	5	9.10	348.8	-70.3
70	SYDBG13-28	386.62	186.30	-15.30	178.40	-33.90	L-PW	6	2.10	115.9	-75
69	SYDBG13-24	386.48	184.10	-10.40	177.90	-28.60	M-RW	7	11.00	116.4	-71.7
68	SYDBG13-20	384.95	224.40	-41.80	223.80	-66.80	H-N	7	8.00	340.3	-54.2
67	SYDBG13-22	384.93	199.30	-4.30	196.10	-26.60	H-NW	8	7.00	69.2	-65.7
66	SYDBG13-23	384.92	199.70	-44.00	178.90	-64.70	L-QSTV	9	11.50	286.7	-76.9

65	SYDBG13-17	384.82	184.60	-15.00	176.60	-33.00	K-RW	9	13.80	122	-74.2
64	SYDBG13-11	384.08	179.60	-22.20	168.10	-38.10	G-N	8	7.60	154.1	-74
63	SYDBG13-13	384.07	140.40	-24.30	129.10	-24.10	G-MW	8	8.20	188.2	-39.3
62	SYDBG13-199	383.27	191.60	-1.80	188.50	-22.40	O-SWX	7	4.30	88.4	-66.8
61	SYDBG11-9	364.73	218.60	-60.60	236.00	-72.60	H-N	7	10.40	329.1	-45.7
60	SYDBG12-37	363.90	150.90	-12.30	147.70	-22.10	N-TX	8	20.20	170.9	-53.2
59	SYDBG12-33	363.88	214.30	-2.80	215.10	-16.00	M-TX	9	14.30	50	-48.9
58	SYDBG12-31A	363.84	203.80	-3.00	204.20	-16.90	O-TX	7	15.50	62.6	-56.6
57	SYDBG12-30A	362.47	193.70	-23.00	193.50	-37.00	F-M	8	5.40	63.6	-72.4
56	SYDBG12-27	362.41	213.90	-10.60	215.30	-23.80	I-S	11	3.30	44.8	-51.6
55	SYDBG12-25	362.39	195.40	-12.10	195.40	-26.10	F-LX	8	9.30	71	-65.8
54	SYDBG11-18	360.43	188.10	-13.70	187.40	-27.60	J-NY	6	14.60	88.6	-70
53	SYDBG12-22A	360.24	139.50	-57.70	139.50	-57.70	K-NY	5	14.70	220.3	-57.1
52	SYDBG12-21	360.23	177.50	-15.60	175.60	-29.00	H-M	6	15.10	123.5	-71.6
51	SYDBG11-25	358.51	164.20	-33.50	157.80	-45.10	K-QY	8	19.00	186.2	-69.7
50	SYDBG11-38A	358.33	209.90	-35.20	213.60	-48.60	TVX-Z	5	20.90	18.6	-61.2
49	SYDBG12-17	358.31	222.00	11.30	221.40	-1.20	I-OX	8	13.40	51.5	-39.1
48	SYDBG12-15	358.29	208.40	-12.50	210.60	-32.80	L-R	7	13.40	42.1	-58.5
47	SYDBG12-14	358.28	198.00	-10.20	198.20	-24.20	J-QY	9	9.20	67.2	-63.4
46	SYDBG11-33	356.58	197.40	-29.00	197.80	-43.00	I-RY	11	11.80	44.1	-72.3
45	SYDBG11-36	356.52	161.50	-17.40	158.00	-28.80	H-NY	8	11.00	163	-63.1
44	SYDBG12-8	353.63	358.10	10.90	356.80	24.20	D-L	9	13.40	298.7	69
43	SYDBG10-3	112.85	33.10	-2.00	33.20	15.00	J-P	7	8.90	232.6	49.9
42	SYDBG10-4	112.84	34.10	22.00	34.90	39.00	R-VX	6	10.00	211.4	57.3
41	SYDBG10-1	112.35	251.80	-19.70	257.70	-31.80	J-NY	6	2.40	11.8	-19.5

40	SYDBG9-5	109.70	39.40	32.10	42.10	48.80	QSUV	4	8.80	194.3	54.2
39	SYDBG9-4	109.65	13.20	18.20	10.50	34.30	H-MX	7	16.00	254.8	72.6
38	SYDBG9-2	109.55	344.10	63.30	306.70	71.00	N-QS-UX	8	14.90	67.7	47.5
37	SYDBG9-7	109.50	41.10	4.30	41.80	21.00	G-MX	8	9.40	220.7	45.6
36	SYDBG8-7A	107.65	51.00	30.00	56.40	45.70	OPR-TX	6	17.20	191.7	41.5
35	SYDBG7-3	88.13	310.90	42.40	295.00	43.30	O-RX	5	22.20	30	33.6
34	SYDBG7-2	88.12	329.00	23.30	321.10	30.60	H-L	5	9.40	3.8	51.2
33	SYDBG6-4	77.72	48.50	41.50	47.60	47.40	E-LX	9	12.70	193.7	49.3
32	SYDBG6-1	77.63	6.30	30.90	3.30	34.50	H-NY	8	11.30	277.7	75.2
31	SYDBG6-7	77.43	23.60	43.50	20.10	48.40	G-NX	9	5.80	208.1	72.4
30	SYDBG6-8	77.33	61.40	34.90	61.70	40.90	R-UW	5	14.20	193.6	35.6
29	SYDBG5-11	70.86	15.30	25.00	13.20	29.50	R-UW	5	12.30	252.9	68.7
28	SYDBG5-10	70.81	31.10	34.10	29.00	39.50	N-VX	10	9.50	216	62.2
27	SYDBG5-15A	70.61	11.50	34.10	8.30	38.20	O-UW	8	6.60	256.5	75.9
26	SYDBG5-8	70.52	0.10	29.00	357.10	32.10	O-T	6	4.10	299.9	73.7
25	SYDBG5-7	70.51	318.00	36.50	313.70	35.30	P-VX	8	5.60	13.2	46.7
24	SYDBG5-14	70.31	4.10	13.50	2.80	17.10	P-SUVX	7	3.70	283.4	65.1
23	SYDBG5-5	70.29	147.60	-12.60	146.30	-12.50	O-T	6	4.20	166.5	-48.6
22	SYDBG5-4	70.27	38.00	13.20	37.40	18.80	P-VX	8	18.40	226	48.2
21	SYDBG5-13	69.79	23.60	35.70	20.90	40.70	R-UW	5	4.10	223.8	69
20	SYDBG5-2	69.77	16.40	36.10	13.20	40.50	O-R	4	5.00	238.4	74.4
19	SYDBG5-1	69.75	15	39.8	11.3	44.1	R-UX	5	7.2	235	77.6
18	SYDBG3-7	53.00	353.10	-19.50	354.00	7.40	J-MO-QY	8	7.70	301.9	59.7
17	SYDBG3-9	52.96	350.30	23.80	341.60	49.50	H-OX	9	12.80	13.6	74.1
16	SYDBG3-4A	52.70	37.90	39.50	59.90	61.90	F-LX	8	15.40	169.8	43

15	SYDBG3-6A	52.66	39.00	25.90	51.70	49.00	D-I	6	3.30	190.1	46.3
14	SYDBG3-1	52.55	2.50	14.10	0.20	41.80	G-LX	7	10.40	288.9	80.6
13	SYDBG3-2A	52.53	357.10	27.90	349.90	54.80	F-J	5	2.30	35.2	81.5
12	SYDBG3-10A	52.51	313.20	13.50	303.80	27.20	L-OY	5	12.50	13.6	35.9
11	SYDBG2-9A	3.62	346.50	30.20	347.60	49.10	L-TX	10	14.60	5	78.9
10	SYDBG2-8A	3.61	40.40	14.90	46.40	24.30	TVXab	5	8.00	214.9	43
9	SYDBG2-10	3.38	358.40	21.60	1.70	39.80	G-OX	10	11.60	281.7	79
8	SYDBG2-6A	3.38	28.80	34.10	41.50	45.90	KLN-P	5	5.50	198.5	53.9
7	SYDBG2-3A	3.22	21.80	36.10	34.50	49.70	K-O	5	5.00	196.3	60.7
6	SYDBG2-1	3.20	354.90	32.20	359.00	50.60	G-LW	7	9.00	311.5	87.7
5	SYDBG1-8	1.35	11.50	7.10	14.10	23.60	N-SW	7	8.30	255.4	65.2
4	SYDBG1-15	1.18	4.30	21.40	8.80	38.90	O-UWZb	10	7.20	253.8	76.1
3	SYDBG1-10A	1.15	354.00	25.50	356.90	44.10	K- PRTVX11	14		310.2	81.9
2	SYDBG1-3	1.10	16.40	41.30	30.50	55.90	K-O	5	11.10	184.6	64.9
1	SYDBG1-9	1.09	355.20	-10.80	355.00	7.80	J-N	5	7.00	300	60.1

Table S7. Paleomagnetic results from principal component analysis of the Juanlingcao specimens.

No.	Spec.	H (m)	D_Geog.	I_Geog.	D_Strat.	I_Strat.	points	N	MAD	VGP_Plon.	VGP_Plat.
147	SYJLC26-8	966.33	1	8.4	6.2	28.1	H-N	7	10.8	271.7	70.6
146	SYJLC26-5	964.33	178.7	-45.5	204.7	-63.3	H-KM	5	6	341.9	-67.9
145	SYJLC26-1	963.18	192.5	-19.6	203	-34.9	J-O	6	8.1	49.1	-65
144	SYJLC24-15	941.13	214.4	-32.9	228.1	-50.4	I-O	7	6.1	9.7	-49.6
143	SYJLC24-12	936.13	186.6	-26.3	189	-49.1	J-P	7	3.1	42.2	-81.6
142	SYJLC24-2	923.43	193.4	-20	197	-42.2	I-O	7	3.1	47.1	-72.6
141	SYJLC23-5	896.89	180	14.8	180	-8.2	S-X	6	10.3	110	-60.6
140	SYJLC23-2	896.54	240.7	-5.5	244.7	-16.3	N-S	6	15.2	27.2	-25.6
139	SYJLC22-8	892.50	174.9	-49.7	169.1	-72.5	J-O	6	2.4	276.4	-64.6
138	SYJLC21-5	865.61	29.2	13.4	34.5	33	N-W	10	4.1	218	55.5
137	SYJLC20-5	833.03	70.1	13.6	76.9	20.3	M-S	7	13.2	198.3	16.6
136	SYJLC19-27	821.00	3.2	1.6	3.5	24.5	S-W	5	16.7	280.4	69.1
135	SYJLC19-23	819.00	28.7	13.1	33.8	32.8	G-M	7	11.3	218.9	56
134	SYJLC19-20	817.00	10	20.5	12.8	43.1	M-U	9	6.2	233.8	76
133	SYJLC19-18	815.00	47	21.5	57.1	35.8	S-W	5	3.9	199.9	37.8
132	SYJLC19-17	815.00	359.1	13.8	358.9	36.8	T-Y	5	11.9	294.6	77
131	SYJLC19-11	812.00	355.9	-12.6	355.9	10.3	R-W	6	14.8	298.6	61.4
130	SYJLC19-8	811.00	27.4	5.5	30.6	25.6	H-N	7	7.8	228.4	55.8
129	SYJLC19-5	809.00	12.5	-9.6	12.7	12.8	U-X	4	13.5	263.6	60.5
128	SYJLC19-1	807.50	359	38.9	358.3	61.9	L-X	13	10.8	102.6	80.3
127	SYJLC18-5	798.32	35.5	-13.5	34.6	5.4	L-W	12	2.9	236.2	45.4
126	SYJLC18-1	797.12	27.5	6.7	30.9	26.9	L-U	10	8.1	227	56
125	SYJLC16-8	781.86	142.5	-23.5	132.7	-40.6	L-S	8	10.3	198.7	-47.5

124	SYJLC15-8	769.30	8.6	-19	8.7	3	O-V	8	4.9	273.9	57
123	SYJLC15-5	768.51	333	8.9	328.6	26.1	O-V	8	1.6	352.9	55.3
122	SYJLC15-2	765.41	21.9	15.2	24.3	36.6	I-N	6	4.9	225.2	64.8
121	SYJLC14-6	750.87	339	18.5	332.4	36.8	R-V	5	15.1	359.1	62.3
120	SYJLC14-1	750.27	37.8	14.5	42.9	33.6	Q-V	6	2.5	210.6	48.9
119	SYJLC13-9	745.00	31.2	-30.5	28.5	-9.8	Q-V	6	3.6	249.4	43
118	SYJLC13-5	743.60	20.5	-0.5	21.2	21.1	Q-V	6	4.1	244.4	60.2
117	SYJLC13-2	743.25	24.2	-14.6	23.8	6.7	Q-V	6	3.6	248.5	52.6
116	SYJLC12-8	726.74	31	2.7	31.1	25.7	N-U	8	4.2	227.8	55.4
115	SYJLC12-2	724.24	16.6	2.7	15.2	25	S-V	4	4.4	252.2	65.4
114	SYJLC11-9	701.26	1.6	8.8	357.6	28.8	G-N	8	6.4	297.4	71.7
113	SYJLC11-6	700.06	351.8	-2.6	350.1	15.4	E-N	10	7.1	311.8	62.8
112	SYJLCK-12	693.20	351.3	1.9	349.1	17.4	H-N	7	5.3	314.7	63.4
111	SYJLCK-11	693.10	344.6	7.8	340.7	21.4	H-N	7	4.8	332.8	61.5
110	SYJLCK-7	692.70	344.1	-4.4	343.5	9.5	H-N	7	4	321.7	57.4
109	SYJLCK-2	690.10	23.5	28.6	21.4	48.4	H-N	7	3.7	206.9	71.3
108	SYJLC10-3	678.48	55.3	27.6	61.5	39.4	N-S	6	12.1	194.9	35.3
107	SYJLC8-31	632.93	178.6	-23.9	171.3	-40.4	I-N	6	3.1	148.4	-77.1
106	SYJLC8-30	631.48	150.3	-42	130.9	-49.2	P-T	5	10.5	209.1	-48.5
105	SYJLC8-23	629.12	183	-45.4	167.2	-62	I-O	7	2.3	248	-76
104	SYJLC8-19	627.16	198.2	-32.1	193.8	-51.5	H-M	6	5.8	22.8	-78.3
103	SYJLC8-17	625.63	216.7	-35.5	219.6	-55.3	M-T	8	5.9	4.5	-57.6
102	SYJLC8-14	624.25	167.8	-52.8	140	-64.4	F-L	7	7.5	234.8	-57.2
101	SYJLC8-12	622.90	195.1	-33.5	189.3	-52.6	K-Q	7	4.6	19.8	-82.2
100	SYJLC8-7	622.70	198.1	-32.5	193.6	-51.9	H-N	7	4	21.1	-78.6
99	SYJLC8-5	622.60	199	-31.2	195.1	-50.7	H-N	7	8.4	25.1	-77.1

98	SYJLC8-1	621.91	346	-8.3	349.8	-8.3	S-XY	7	1.1	306.3	51.1
97	SYJLC7-5	606.92	302.8	31.3	290.8	30.2	K-O	5	11.5	22.9	26
96	SYJLC7-2	606.89	9.5	34.5	1.6	52.7	H-M	6	3.5	209	88.6
95	SYJLC6-5	597.90	11.9	18	8.3	36.8	H-M	6	3	258.4	75.1
94	SYJLC6-2	597.75	9.8	6.3	7.8	24.9	H-L	5	7.3	269	68.4
93	SYJLC6-2	597.75	333	-10.5	334.4	0.7	Q-U	5	13	331.3	49.1
92	SYJLC5-11	577.90	2.5	22.4	356.4	39.7	H-M	6	4.6	307.1	78.6
91	SYJLC5-6	577.11	354.4	30.5	344	45.8	I-N	6	6.3	359.7	74.9
90	SYJLC5-3	576.53	328.5	35.8	312.9	43	J-O	6	6.5	21	48.4
89	SYJLC5-1	576.53	39.5	30	42.8	49.7	H-M	6	3.5	192.7	53.8
88	SYJLC4-9	560.15	13.8	26.1	9.2	45.1	M-Q	5	7.7	238.3	79.5
87	SYJLC4-6	559.16	10.2	13.5	7.1	32.1	S-X	6	10.7	266.6	72.7
86	SYJLC3-31	554.22	18.8	51.7	8.3	71	N-R	5	4	122.3	67.3
85	SYJLC3-18	547.44	106.6	-23	99.5	-17.2	S-W	5	8.8	202.2	-12.7
84	SYJLC3-8	541.74	4.4	26.9	357.3	44.5	R-W	6	12.4	308.4	82.3
83	SYJLC3-4	537.11	349.8	15.2	344.1	29.9	J-O	6	11.4	333.3	67.4
82	SYJLC3-2	535.81	9.8	52.2	351.9	69.9	J-P	7	3.7	96.6	68.9
81	SYJLC2-27	525.62	340.5	28.2	329.4	39.7	K-O	5	5.8	5.8	61
80	SYJLC2-23	522.57	18.8	9.2	17.4	28.8	R-V	5	3.1	244.8	66
79	SYJLC2-15	520.07	7.9	1.5	6.5	20	Q-T	4	7.3	274.1	66.1
78	SYJLC2-10	518.07	31.5	17.8	31.8	37.8	K-Q	7	4.9	215.5	59.4
77	SYJLC1-78	507.13	190.6	-11.1	188	-15	H-L	5	6.7	92.3	-63.1
76	SYJLC1-69	501.08	16.5	13.3	13.4	18.4	F-JLM	7	3.1	259.8	63
75	SYJLC1-66	499.43	357.2	34.8	348.7	35.5	N-PS-U	6	6.6	328.8	72.9
74	SYJLC1-62	494.63	343.5	65.9	319.9	62.1	D-K	8	6.7	49.6	57.4
73	SYJLC1-54	489.96	4.3	61.7	341.5	62.3	F-M	8	4.4	60.5	72.4

72	SYJLC1-46	485.96	348	34.4	340	33.1	G-J	4	4.4	344.2	66.4
71	SYJLC1-43	484.91	149.9	-48	138.9	-42.8	S-V	4	12.4	197.4	-53.3
70	SYJLC1-34	479.05	205.2	-49.8	191.2	-55.5	F-J	5	12	1.4	-80.5
69	SYJLC1-11	470.18	173.4	-30.7	166.2	-30.6	M-R	6	8.3	149.5	-68.9
68	SYJLC1-1	468.46	141.2	-43	132.8	-36.4	Q-V	6	9.3	194.7	-46.3
67	SYTJG6-33	453.40	0.6	16.5	0.7	23.5	H-L	5	4.4	288.1	68.8
66	SYTJG6-37	452.66	7.1	14	7.5	20.9	R-W	6	6	271.4	66.3
65	SYTJG6-29	452.46	24.3	20.8	25.8	27	R-W	6	9.8	233.2	59.7
64	SYTJG6-25	452.10	138.3	38.1	141.3	32.5	I-N	6	4.6	151.9	-26.9
63	SYTJG6-24	451.20	60.6	-19.2	58.7	-16	P-V	7	14.5	225.4	20.5
62	SYTJG6-21	451.20	30.1	28	32.4	33.8	P-W	8	5.1	219.2	57.4
61	SYTJG6-17	450.63	11.5	14.5	12.1	21.2	O-W	9	1.9	261	64.9
60	SYTJG6-9	448.69	24.2	-8.1	23.9	-1.9	S-W	5	9.1	252	48.9
59	SYTJG6-6	443.09	9.9	18.2	10.5	25	H-P	9	6.8	262.4	67.5
58	SYTJG6-1	442.59	348.4	26.7	347.8	33.6	P-W	8	6.8	328.8	71.4
57	SYTJG5-282	397.48	185.8	-30.8	176.9	-51.7	H-N	7	8.4	176.8	-87.2
56	SYTJG5-275	396.58	201.1	-17.7	199.6	-40.6	F-J	5	9.4	45.9	-70
55	SYTJG5-270	395.97	228.3	-23.8	234.9	-44.8	F-J	5	6	13.3	-42.4
54	SYTJG5-267	394.74	245.7	-33.7	260.8	-49.9	J-M	4	15.4	357.6	-23.4
53	SYTJG5-262	392.98	230.3	-12.6	234.6	-33.5	F-O	10	7	23.1	-39.2
52	SYTJG5-260	392.98	173.2	-27.4	162.3	-45.4	F-N	9	3.9	181.3	-73.4
51	SYTJG5-257	392.35	179.9	7.3	179.4	-13.2	J-O	6	4	111.3	-63.2
50	SYTJG5-250	391.07	158.2	-31.4	143	-44.4	N-V	9	5.6	196.9	-57.2
49	SYTJG5-248	391.07	173.8	-47.2	149.4	-63.8	O-U	7	8	236.2	-63.7
48	SYTJG5-245	390.55	197	-37	191.1	-59.4	S-W	5	9.4	339.7	-78.9
47	SYTJG5-237	390.02	195.2	-27.9	190.6	-50.3	T-Y	6	6.3	32.4	-80.7

46	SYTJG5-232	388.08	192.5	-1.7	191.1	-24	G-O	9	3.7	81.6	-66.7
45	SYTJG5-228	387.01	242.6	-35.3	258	-52.3	F-M	8	9.8	356.5	-26.4
44	SYTJG5-186	377.04	188.8	-33.7	180	-55.1	K-S	9	6.5	290	-87.9
43	SYTJG5-171	372.11	194	-12	191.6	-34.3	K-U	11	12.2	71.9	-72
42	SYTJG5-155	367.32	186	-45.1	169.5	-65.4	F-M	8	5.3	263.7	-73.9
41	SYTJG5-151	366.11	204.3	-35.8	202.8	-58.8	H-R	11	9.6	355.1	-70.8
40	SYTJG5-145	364.83	207.9	-35.7	208.4	-58.7	O-U	7	4.8	357.2	-66.5
39	SYTJG5-142	363.65	202.5	-3.4	202	-26.3	K-O	5	9.6	59.2	-62
38	SYTJG5-286	361.71	179.4	-38.2	164.7	-57.2	K-N	4	6.2	223.5	-76.9
37	SYTJG5-136	361.71	192.1	-41.4	181.7	-63.1	H-N	7	6.1	296.3	-78.8
36	SYTJG5-134	361.66	226.4	-3.8	228.5	-25.3	M-R	6	11	32.7	-41.7
35	SYTJG5-123	360.25	170.6	-42.7	149.7	-58.8	I-R	10	6.4	222.8	-65
34	SYTJG5-111	357.90	201.1	-23.4	199.1	-46.2	J-Q	8	3.4	34.9	-72.5
33	SYTJG5-106	356.85	180.1	-9.9	176	-30.1	I-MOP	7	13.1	122.7	-72.3
32	SYTJG5-102	356.20	171	-22.7	161.7	-40.3	J-O	6	13.9	171.5	-70.8
31	SYTJG5-99	355.45	177.3	-35.6	163.4	-54.2	K-T	10	5.3	209.8	-76.2
30	SYTJG5-93	354.15	139.8	-45.8	114.2	-49.9	S-V	4	15.6	216.4	-35.1
29	SYTJG5-86	351.85	212.6	-34.1	215.5	-57	O-U	7	6.2	1.6	-61
28	SYTJG5-75	349.70	213.8	12.6	213.7	-10.3	F-J	5	8.4	54.6	-47.8
27	SYTJG5-79	348.35	189.7	-44	176.4	-65.2	P-V	7	3.7	279.9	-76
26	SYTJG5-63	346.75	147.6	-42	129	-43.2	QS-V	5	17.3	203.3	-45.2
25	SYTJG5-54	344.23	176.3	-21.1	168	-33.3	J-P	7	8.6	148	-71.3
24	SYTJG5-48	343.48	172	-21.3	163.4	-32.2	P-V	7	6.4	157	-68.1
23	SYTJG5-43	342.30	242.7	-50	257	-68.3	F-M	8	10.5	336.5	-33.3
22	SYTJG5-31	340.62	199.6	-24.7	193.2	-42.4	I-M	5	3.3	54.4	-75.4
21	SYTJG5-24	339.64	203.9	-15.3	200.3	-33.8	F-M	8	5.5	54.5	-66.5

20	SYTJG5-18	338.97	201.3	-3.1	199.5	-21.4	G-N	8	9	66.9	-61.3
19	SYTJG5-4	337.00	139.8	-36.7	125	-35.7	N-T	7	8.1	198.8	-39.5
18	SYTJG4-31	326.06	174.3	-43.9	166.8	-56.5	M-RU- W	9	11.9	222.1	-78.7
17	SYTJG4-30	325.21	106.8	-43.6	93.8	-42	E-K	7	8.1	218.8	-16.1
16	SYTJG4-27	325.16	195.6	-33.1	195.2	-47.1	M-S	7	12.5	37.8	-76
15	SYTJG4-39	325.08	121.4	-26.7	114	-29.3	L-U	10	13.5	200.6	-28.4
14	SYTJG4-9	320.06	215.7	-30.1	219.4	-43.2	J-O	6	7	23.2	-54.9
13	SYTJG4-12	320.06	206.7	-19	208	-32.8	L-R	7	15.7	45	-60.5
12	SYTJG4-15	319.86	204.8	-50.8	208.6	-64.6	I-O	7	7	340.6	-64.7
11	SYTJG4-4	317.10	105.2	34.2	114.7	33.5	F-I	5	2.9	170.9	-9.1
10	SYTJG4-2	317.06	73.4	-2.7	73.7	5	G-M	8	14.9	207	14.9
9	SYTJG3-6	70.44	56.7	20.5	65.4	22	R-V	5	11.2	203.9	26.7
8	SYTJG3-2	70.36	37.5	22	47.7	30.5	H-L	5	12.3	209.7	44
7	SYTJG2-13	16.21	27	-28.9	20.4	-14.3	P-U	6	13.6	260.8	44.9
6	SYTJG2-13	16.21	31.4	-1.3	32.9	10.7	J-O	6	9.8	235.3	48.5
5	SYTJG2-4	14.41	350.1	10.2	352.5	31.3	W-a	5	12.4	314	72.1
4	SYTJG2-1	14.41	350.8	17	354.3	38.1	W-a	5	13.4	314.1	76.9
3	SYTJG1-16	2.30	14.6	29.6	26.8	45.1	S-Z	8	8.5	209.4	65.9
2	SYTJG1-15	1.75	34.8	20.4	44.3	30	N-Y	12	5.8	212.5	46.6
1	SYTJG1-4	1.04	43.2	14.4	50	21.4	M-V	10	5.5	214	39.2

Table S8. Paleomagnetic results from principal component analysis of the Niupanggou specimens.

No.	Specimen	H (m)	D_Geog.	I_Geog.	D_Strat.	I_Strat.	points	N	MAD	VGP_Plon.	VGP_Plat.
40	SYNPG11-40	280.03	253.9	-30.4	255.6	-43.2	K-N	4	19.1	5.3	-25
39	SYNPG11-36	277.48	23	16.5	19.5	25.9	I-M	5	7.9	243.6	63.4
38	SYNPG11-24	271.13	46.2	-2.2	45.9	10.2	M-T	8	5.8	223.3	38.9
37	SYNPG11-20	269.03	34.7	3.7	33.6	14.9	I-M	5	6.5	232.2	49.6
36	SYNPG11-16	267.43	6.1	36.4	356.5	42.2	H-N	7	3.9	309.5	80.4
35	SYNPG11-13	265.60	16.2	14.4	12.9	23.1	H-M	6	7.8	258.2	65.5
34	SYNPG11-11	263.08	299.4	49.9	289.3	41.4	I-N	6	11	31.1	28.3
33	SYNPG11-2	259.31	2.4	36.9	352.5	41.9	F-L	7	6	327	78.6
32	SYNPG9-3	234.84	185.8	-21	180.7	-27.2	R-V	5	13.9	107.9	-70.9
31	SYNPG7-6	169.25	9	22.7	1.3	29.9	G-N	8	2.7	285.8	72.5
30	SYNPG7-4	169.25	15.2	27.9	5.9	36.6	G-N	8	4.5	266.8	75.9
29	SYNPG7-3	164.25	64.8	23.2	63.7	40.1	K-N	4	11.8	193.2	33.7
28	SYNPG7-1	164.10	308.3	41.9	298.1	31.6	L-P	5	10.4	19.8	32.5
27	SYNPG6-8	174.46	34.7	31.6	26.2	44.8	J-P	7	5.3	210.4	66.3
26	SYNPG6-5	172.88	38	32.9	29.6	46.7	G-L	6	4.3	204.3	64.1
25	SYNPG5-1	168.71	27.2	19.7	21.3	31.6	H-M	6	4.7	235.4	64.8
24	SYNPG4-27	162.52	23.2	-3.6	22.7	8	J-O	6	7.1	249.4	53.8
23	SYNPG4-14	154.03	355.6	14	350.8	17.9	I-N	6	6.2	311.3	64.2
22	SYNPG3-14	108.38	335.3	31	325.7	28.1	J-S	10	10.5	357.5	53.9
21	SYNPG3-8	100.82	355	13.2	350.5	17	K-S	9	10.1	311.6	63.7
20	SYNPG3-5	97.82	20.1	3.7	18	14.5	J-N	5	4.6	253.5	59
19	SYNPG2-46	65.51	210.3	-37.9	198.6	-49.9	H-P	9	9.1	25	-74
18	SYNPG2-32	54.26	19.3	15.2	14.2	25.4	Q-U	5	8.4	254	66.1

17	SYNPG2-29	54.26	5.8	29.6	355.5	35.7	Q-U	5	10.5	307.4	75.7
16	SYNPG2-26	53.96	29.2	17.6	24	30	P-U	6	8.8	232.9	62.2
15	SYNPG2-24	50.96	16.7	2.7	14.8	12.7	Q-V	6	3.7	259.8	59.6
14	SYNPG2-21	47.41	18.6	50.8	356.8	58.9	S-V	4	7.2	88.3	83.3
13	SYNPG2-17	46.91	3.3	29.8	353	35.1	H-O	8	8.4	315.6	74.5
12	SYNPG2-14	44.41	49.6	38.4	42.4	54	I-O	7	9.3	186.1	55.1
11	SYNPG2-8	41.91	357	19.7	350.4	23.8	I-N	6	4.3	314.8	67.2
10	SYNPG2-8	41.91	355.9	7.9	352.9	12.2	P-V	7	5.8	305.1	61.9
9	SYNPG2-2	34.41	303.4	35.2	296	24.2	Q-U	5	15.1	16.5	28.5
8	SYNPG1-40	27.19	292	49.5	283.2	43.9	R-V	5	13.7	35.8	24.3
7	SYNPG1-31	19.79	29.5	29.1	26.8	38.2	J-Q	8	6.1	220	63.5
6	SYNPG1-29	16.29	23.3	18.8	21.2	27.5	M-Q	5	6.2	239.4	63.1
5	SYNPG1-26	13.19	72	-3.5	72.1	5.9	J-M	4	4.3	207.6	16.5
4	SYNPG1-20	6.09	194.6	-42.5	187.8	-50.1	S-W	5	14.6	39.5	-82.9
3	SYNPG1-17	4.44	223.6	-6.6	223.3	-16.6	G-N	8	4.2	42	-43
2	SYNPG1-14	3.16	214.9	-4.8	214.4	-14.3	G-M	7	9.5	51.7	-48.8
1	SYNPG1-7	1.50	203.3	-12.8	201.7	-21.6	T-W	4	5.3	63.2	-60.1

Table S9. Paleomagnetic results for the conglomerate test of the Dongbeigou section.

No.	Spec.	H (m)	D_Geog.	I_Geog.	D_Strat.	I_Strat.	points	N	MAD
1	SYDBG4G-2-1	71.63	142.9	-5.7	142.3	-5.7	J-O	6	5.2
2	SYDBG4G-4-1	77.63	157.2	-32	153.4	-33.3	P-U	6	15.3
3	SYDBG4G-4-2	77.63	171.6	-60.4	161.4	-62.8	GJ-N	6	12.7
4	SYDBG4G-5-1	80.63	345	-4.2	345.3	-1.9	G-L	6	6.9
5	SYDBG4G-6-1	83.63	18.4	43.8	14.6	48.7	F-K	6	5.5
6	SYDBG4G-7-1	86.63	305.2	26.7	302.4	24.7	R-U	4	4.1
7	SYDBG4G-7-2A	86.68	288.1	34.5	285	30.9	M-P	4	4.1

H (m) is the stratigraphic thickness of the specimen in the Dongbeigou section. D_Geog. and I_Geog. (D_Strat. and I_Strat.) are the declination and inclination of the characteristic remanent magnetization (ChRM) in the geographic (stratigraphic) coordinate. N is the number of steps (points) used to calculate the line-anchored best-fit magnetization (ChRM) vector described by its maximum angular deviation (MAD). The virtual geomagnetic pole (VGP_Plon., VGP_Plat.) was calculated. The points are the steps of thermal demagnetization, from A to W corresponding to NRM, 80°C, 150°C, 200°C, 250°C, 300°C, 350°C, 400°C, 450°C, 500°C, 550°C, 585°C, 600°C, 610°C, 620°C, 630°C, 640°C, 650°C, 660°C, 670°C, 680°C, 690°C, and origin, respectively.

Table S10. Forty-four stratigraphic sampling levels of dinosaur eggshell fossils from the Niupanggou and Juanlingcao sections in the Shanyang Basin.

Level	<i>Macroolithus yaotunensis</i>	<i>Elongatoolithus elongatus</i>	<i>Stromatoolithus pinglingensis</i>	Thickness (m)_NPG	Thickness (m)_converted
1				Juanlingcao section	360.00
2				3.12	478.00
3				4.30	479.00
4				26.00	497.39
5				32.84	503.19
6				42.47	511.35
7				45.01	513.50
8				47.55	515.66
9				50.09	517.81
10				52.63	519.96
11				55.17	522.11
12				57.70	524.26
13				64.49	530.01
14				65.49	530.86
15				73.14	537.34
16				75.29	539.17
17				77.44	540.99
18				80.32	543.43
19				84.16	546.68
20				96.05	556.76
21				96.68	557.29
22				97.32	557.83
23				98.86	559.14
24				100.40	560.44
25				101.94	561.75
26				103.48	563.05
27				105.03	564.37
28				106.59	565.69
29				108.15	567.01
30				109.91	568.51
31				116.60	574.17
32				131.19	586.54
33				136.63	591.15
34				141.87	595.59
35				147.30	600.19
36				149.37	601.94
37				149.87	602.37
38				164.25	614.55
39				167.72	617.50
40				168.90	618.50
41				169.25	618.79
42				169.49	619.00
43				169.50	619.00
44				170.05	619.47

Note:The thickness of stratigraphic levels containing dinosaur fossils in the Niupanggou and Juanlingcao sections (Thickness(m)_NPG) were converted to the thickness of the integrated section of the Shanyang Basin (Thickness(m)_converted) according to their polarities and lithologies with linear interpolations.

Table S11. The Late Cretaceous dinosaur occurrences around the world.

Area	Total number of occurrences	Country	Number of Occurrences
North America	1099	United States	552
		Canada	531
		Mexico	16
East Asia	432	China	133
		Mongolia	279
		Russian	19
		Japan	1
Euro	58	Denmark	1
		France	17
		Netherlands	7
		Romania	6
		Spain	21
		United Kingdom	5
		Belgium	1
South America	24	Argentina	24
Central East	17	Uzbekistan	14
		Kazakstan	3
Oceania	4	Australia	4
Africa	2	Madagascar	2

The data derive from Condamine *et al.* (16).

Table S12. The sources of dinosaur reconstruction used in Figure 4 of the main text

Picture	Dinosaur	Source	Artist
	Dromaeosauridae	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-021-23754-0	Fred Wierum, Debivort , and Jack Mayer Wood
	Hadrosauridae		
	Tyrannosauridae		
	Ankylosauria		
	Ornithomimidae	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-017-05272-6	Masato Hattori
	Sauropoda	http://www.cnkonglong.com/h-nd-189.html	Chuang Zhao
	Alvarezsauridae	http://www.ivpp.cas.cn/xwdt/tpxw/201811/t20181103_5153916.html	Aijuan Shi
	Ornithopoda	Wikimedia Commons https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Shantungosaurus-v4.jpg	Debivort
	Oviraptoridae	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-017-05016-6/figures/5	Chuang Zhao

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